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METHODOLOGICAL AND DATA INFRASTRUCTURE REPORT ON YOUTH

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of live or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

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1. Aim, scope, project context, and IPOLIS short description

The Innovative tools and protocols for poverty and living conditions research work package (WP20)

This work package is part of the 'Poverty and living conditions' pillar. Its objectives (among others) are (Gábos & Kopasz, 2014):

- to synthesise and make accessible data and knowledge in a structured form that backs comparative research on social policies, and improves infrastructure for reaching vulnerable groups at risk of poverty;
- to organise indicators and research results in a theoretical frame, with the aim of avoiding bottlenecks and temptations to carry out purely data driven research on poverty and living conditions.

Nine specific vulnerable groups in total are identified:

- easy-to-reach groups: (a) children (0-17 years), (b) youth (15-30 years) and (c) older people (65+ years);
- hard-to-identify groups: (d) migrants, (e) Roma, (f) travellers;
- hard-to-reach groups: (g) institutionalised individuals, (h) undocumented immigrants, and (i) homeless people.

Tasks to be carried out within the WP:

- task 20.1: building an Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System (IPOLIS);
- task 20.2: optimising the use of census microdata to analyse and monitor poverty and living conditions at the territorial level in Europe;
- task 20.3: identifying priorities for future data collection.

Related deliverables and milestones:

- D20.1: conceptual report for IPOLIS;
- D20.2: complete IPOLIS database for vulnerable groups.

This document provides a methodological and data infrastructure proposal for the youth module of the Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System (IPOLIS) (Gábos & Kopasz, 2014). As part of the InGRID project, the Poverty and living conditions pillar (see short description in the box on this page) aims to provide a data infrastructure named IPOLIS to improve the monitoring and analysis of the situation of the most vulnerable population groups in Europe.

The Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System (IPOLIS) helps to identify key issues, challenges, and gaps to inform policy on the situation of children, youth, and the elderly in the field of poverty, living conditions, and quality of life (see short description in the box on the next page). It proposes to serve as a foundation for regularly monitoring progress on policy targets. These targets provide a basis for assessing policy effectiveness and impact, and supports research on quality of life for children, youth, and the elderly. Furthermore, the relationships between quality-of-life indicators can be observed and cross-country patterns according to poverty, living conditions, and quality of life can be detected. Thus, these indicators can be used by a range of stakeholders, including researchers, practitioners, policy makers, non-governmental organisation (NGO) experts, journalists, and students.

In line with the general framework of IPOLIS, the indicators of the youth module (see also the child module by Gábos & Kopasz, 2015):

1. Are based on the concept of Quality of Life. Quality of life was defined as a multi-dimensional concept comprising objective and subjective perception of objective measures (European Commission, 2012: 17). Thus, the youth module includes indicators on objective living condi-

- tions (such as income, homeownership, etc.) and subjective perceptions about objective factors (such as self-perceived health).
2. Consider that each stage of the life cycle has its own characteristics, and therefore special attention is given to age-group-specific problems. This is reflected in the introduction of youth-specific indicators (such as living together with parents, or risk behaviours) and using specific age bands (15-19, 20-24, and 25-29) for all indicators. However, the challenges that result from youth transitions are large and often unmet by the available data sources, as will be discussed further in the recommendations in Chapter 7.
 3. Aim to be *comprehensive and coherent* in offering indicators for all components and subcomponents in the dimensions of: (a) material living conditions; (b) labour market attachment and work-life balance; (c) education and training; (d) health and risk behaviours; (e) social connectedness and civic participation; and (f) environmental quality and physical safety. In this sense, the indicators of the youth module enable comparisons between member states. In connection with other parts of the Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System - especially the key aspects of the economic, social, and policy contexts - these indicators provide information on external factors and national contexts that influence quality of life for youth, as well as provide a reference point on quality of life for comparison to other population groups (e.g. children and the elderly).
 4. Include *all countries of the EU28 within the time period of 2004 to 2013* (or the latest year available at the time of data upload to the database).
 5. Provide a *disaggregation of all indicators* across (several) basic socio-demographic characteristics (i.e. age, gender, income) to reflect that young people represent a heterogeneous group.
 6. Rely on, and are conditioned by, the *availability of existing data* from the European Statistical System (ESS) (EU-SILC; EU-LFS; UOE) and other data sources in selecting specific indicators (ESS, COD, and WDI).

The Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System (IPOLIS)

IPOLIS will be the core outcome of the work package on innovative tools and protocols for poverty and living conditions research of the InGRID project. Work Package 20 is part of the 'Poverty and living conditions' pillar of the project and integrates the research activity within the pillar. The aim of the work package is to build a platform to improve infrastructure for monitoring, analysing, and evaluating the situation of the most vulnerable groups. The Integrated Poverty and Living Conditions Indicator System (IPOLIS) will be produced for the easy-to-reach vulnerable groups: children, youth, and older people. However, the flexible nature of the proposed structure and the implementation plan of IPOLIS allows for the inclusion of other vulnerable groups (e.g. disabled persons, migrants), when they become coherently identifiable in a large data infrastructure, and robust indicators will be ready for production. For the hard-to-identify and hard-to-reach vulnerable groups, protocols will be developed for the creation of a database at a later stage.

Overall this document not only provides a full indicator proposal for the youth module of IPOLIS, but it also prepares an indicator fiche for each and every proposed indicator and makes ready the setup of the IPOLIS database's youth module for all countries and years specified. For this, Chapter 2 outlines the policy context of monitoring youth's quality of life. In Chapters 3 and 4, we take an inventory of existing (inter)national infrastructures and data sources used to provide input or insight for IPOLIS's youth module. The core of the document is Chapter 5, which outlines core definitions and the selection of indicators, and proposes the structure of the youth module. Chapter 6 discusses issues and data gaps in the youth module. Chapter 7 provides recommendations for the improvement of measurement and data infrastructures. Finally, in the appendix we provide a first preliminary application of the data, focusing on the impact of the economic and financial crisis on risk of poverty for young people in Europe in 2008.

2. EU-level policy in combating unemployment and poverty among young people since the new millennium

This chapter outlines the policy context of monitoring youth's quality of life. Relevant supra-national institutions for European developments in the 'youth sector' on youth indicators are the European Union (EU)/European Commission (EC) with the Education and Culture Directorate - General (DG EAC)¹ as the executive body and the Council of Europe (CoE).² Both cooperate within the EU-CoE Youth Partnership framework.

Starting in the new millennium,³ the EC and the CoE adopted the Youth Community action programme (2000-2006), the Youth in Action programme (2007-2013), and the EU Youth Strategy (2010-2018) (see appendix 1 for sources, including timeline on conclusions and regulations from 2000-2013).

On April 13, 2000, the EC and the CoE adopted a decision on establishing the 'Youth Community action programme'. Article 1 stated that the programme should 'promote lifelong learning and the building up of the knowledge and skills and competences likely to foster active citizenship and employability' for young people between the ages of 15 and 25 (OJ L 117, 18.5.2000: 5).

One year later the white paper '*A New Impetus for European Youth*' was adopted. In the white paper, the EC identified four priority themes which were partially also suggested beforehand in the Youth Community action programme: (a) participation and education; (b) employment, vocational training, and social inclusion; (c) well-being, individual autonomy, and culture; (d) and European values, mobility, and relations with the rest of the world. At this stage, the *open method of coordination* (OMC) was adopted for youth policy. Following up on the priorities, participation, and information, in April 2003 the EC proposed a set of *common objectives to encourage young people* to become more involved and better informed. Better information for young people is a precondition for better participation and for the development of young people's potential as individuals and citizens. Following this, the *European Youth Portal* was launched in 2004. Only a year later, on May 30, 2005 the *European Youth Pact* was adopted and implemented, addressing the concerns of young people in Europe and promoting active citizenship. The Pact consisted of three strands: (a) employment, integration, and social advancement; (b) education, training, and mobility; and (c) reconciliation of family and working life, also focusing on employment and integration as important aspects of well-being. Shortly afterwards in 2006,⁴ the '*Youth in Action Programme for the period 2007 to 2013*' was developed and adopted, aiming to develop and support European cooperation in the field of youth. It was designed to encourage young people, especially the most disadvantaged and the disabled, to participate in public life and to promote their sense of initiative, entrepreneurial spirit, and creativity. To this end, the programme defined general and specific objectives that were implemented

1 The DG EAC incorporates two youth units, one on youth policy and one on management of youth in action programme.

2 Next to non-governmental actors and researchers/academics in youth studies.

3 On developments in youth policy before the new millennium see Faché (2012) and Devlin (2010).

4 In 2007 and 2008 the 'Youth in action' programme started along with Eurodesk. A European Youth Week was initiated for the first time. The Agenda 2020 started and the Council stated recommendations on mobility of young volunteers.

through five actions.⁵ The programme focused on young people with fewer opportunities, specifically youth disadvantaged in comparison to their peers in terms of social and economic obstacles (e.g., poverty, disability, educational and cultural difficulties, and health problems).

In 2009 the EC launched the *'EU Youth Strategy 2010-2018'* to promote dialogue between youth and policy makers in order to increase active citizenship, foster social integration, and ensure inclusion of the young in EU policy development. The strategy has two overall objectives: (a) to provide more and equal opportunities for young people in education and in the job market; and (b) to encourage young people to actively participate in society. The strategy proposes initiatives in eight fields of action: (a) education and training; (b) employment and entrepreneurship; (c) health and well-being; (d) participation; (e) voluntary activities; (f) social inclusion; (g) youth and the world; and (h) creativity and culture. One of the main goals combating poverty was prescribed in order to break the intergenerational transmission of poverty and provide equal opportunities for all young people. Young people must be actively involved in all measures promoting social inclusion, as well as engaged in the planning, delivery, and evaluation of the European Year of Combating Poverty and Social Exclusion in 2010. Alongside the strategy, an expert group was installed on youth indicators, which proposed a dashboard of indicators.

Launched in 2010, *'Youth on the Move'* aims to improve young people's education and employability, reduce high youth unemployment, and increase the youth-employment rate. This is in line with the wider EU target of achieving a 75 per cent employment rate for the working-age population (20-64 years) by: (a) making education and training more relevant to young people's needs; (b) encouraging more youth to take advantage of EU grants to study or train in another country; and (c) encouraging EU countries to take measures simplifying the transition from education to work. It is part of the *'Europe 2020 strategy'* (initiated in 2010) for smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth.

The *'Europe 2020 strategy'* focuses strongly on young people, with a headline target of reducing early school leaving and increasing tertiary attainment. Two other headline targets also share a clear youth dimension - reducing the risk of poverty and increasing the share of the population in employment. Part of the 2020 strategy is the *'Youth Employment Package'*, which deals specifically with the situation of young people. It includes measures tackling unacceptable levels of youth unemployment and social exclusion by offering young people jobs, education, and training through the *'Youth Guarantee'*. Under this guarantee, all member states are committed to ensuring that all young people under 25 years of age receive either an offer of employment, continued education, or an apprenticeship or a traineeship within four months after becoming unemployed or leaving formal education. In June 2013, EU leaders agreed to speed up the disbursement of up to € 6 billion to promote jobs for young people under the youth employment initiative. The aid is mainly targeted to regions with a youth unemployment rate above 25 per cent. In order to receive this funding, the beneficiary member states had to adopt plans to tackle youth unemployment, including through implementation of a youth guarantee.

Furthermore, the *'Compact for Growth and Jobs'* agreed upon by the heads of state and government at the European Council in June 2012, includes measures to step up efforts to increase youth employment. Also, in 2012, a Joint Report of the Council and the Commission on the implementation of the *Renewed Framework for European Cooperation in the Youth Field (2010-2018)* was adopted.

In June 2013, leaders also agreed to strengthen initiatives to help young people find jobs or become involved in education across borders, such as the *'Your First EURES Job'* programme and the *'Erasmus+ programme'* (Erasmus for All, 2014-2020), which also promotes cross-border vocational training and has been operational since January 2014.

⁵ These actions included: Youth for Europe (exchanges, initiatives, democratic projects), European voluntary service, Youth in the World (cooperations), Youth Support System (support to bodies, support to European youth forum, training, networking, encouraging projects, information, and partnerships), and support for cooperation in the youth field (meetings, knowledge support, cooperations).

3. Prior efforts to monitor quality of life and well-being for youth

The following chapter describes prior efforts to monitor quality of life and well-being among youth at both international and national levels, and points towards recommendations of EU projects for indicators.⁶

3.1 International level: In the European Union and around the world

Up to now, little effort has been made to monitor the quality of life of youth at the international level:

- alongside the EU Youth Strategy 2010-2018 a *dashboard of EU youth indicators* was developed by experts. The main focus of the dashboard is on social inclusion and participation. These indicators are available up until 2011 on an aggregated level for the EU for individuals aged 0-34 years;
- the OECD's work on youth generated a *scoreboard for youth aged 15-24*, including indicators on labour market attachment and education for all OECD member states in the years 2001 and 2011;
- the United Nations *recommended indicators for the World Programme of Action for Youth* in 2012.

Table 3.1 provides information for each domain of the IPOLIS concept on indicators that are used by the existing indicator systems, including those by the EU and OECD, in comparison to the proposed IPOLIS youth module. Next we introduce the different infrastructures and discuss their shortcomings.

a. EU dashboard of youth indicators

The *dashboard of EU youth indicators* was drawn up in 2011 on the basis of a mandate from the EU Youth Strategy. An expert group⁷ meeting annually contributed to this dashboard, which presents 40 indicators in all eight 'fields of action' of the EU Youth Strategy.⁸ The initial aims of the expert group were to:

- propose a dashboard of indicators in education, employment, social inclusion, and health; and
- provide an overview of new indicators in 'core' youth policy areas where these did not previously exist (e.g. volunteering, youth participation).

In line with this, Eurostat set up a sub-section regarding youth on its website, displaying the latest available data for the dashboard of youth indicators (European Youth Portal:

<http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/page/portal/youth/data/database>). The sub-section includes indicators on population (yth_demo), education and training (yth_educ), employment

6 The ILO (WHAT DOES THIS STAND FOR?) in cooperation with UNICEF generated the youthSTATS database (at <http://www.youthstatistics.org/> [date last accessed 13 April 2015]) on labour market indicators for youth aged 15-29 for most of the Asian and Eastern countries.

7 Another source for the dashboard is the Flash Eurobarometer survey on youth (F1319a and F1319b) in early 2011.

8 The latest version of the dashboard is available at: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/c/portal/layout?p_l_id=749597&p_v_l_s_g_id=0 [date last accessed 13 April 2015].

(yth_empl), health (yth_health), social inclusion (yth_incl), culture and creativity (yth_cult), participation (yth_part), volunteering (yth_volunt), and youth in the digital world (yth_isoc).⁹

The dashboard provides an evidence-based approach to youth policy and helps to identify key issues, challenges, and gaps to inform policy so that youth-related interventions are relevant and directed at those most in need. It also provides a basis for developing and regularly monitoring progress on policy targets, which provides a basis for assessing policy effectiveness and impact. However, the dashboard's indicators enable comparisons between member states, but do not provide information on external factors and national or local contexts (for a critique, see Hadjivassiliou & Rickard, 2013). Comparison without attention to external factors and national or local contexts can lead to misinterpretation of the data. Thus, their use and analysis must take into account any influencing factors and contexts. Furthermore, the attribution of specific interventions to particular outcome indicators is rarely possible. As far as we know, there are no commonly used definitions for some of the 'core' youth policy areas (youth participation) and thus indicators used in these fields of action are not necessarily in line with the policy objectives (Ecorys, 2011: 32). Additionally, there are data gaps in core youth policy areas, such as youth participation, volunteering, creativity, and culture (Ecorys, 2011: 33). One of the main issues is that young people represent a heterogeneous group, thus indicators should be disaggregated across several basic socio-demographic characteristics (i.e. age, gender, socio-economic characteristics, ethnicity, etc.).

b. OECD scoreboard for youth

OECD ministers at their meeting on May 29-30, 2013 agreed on a comprehensive range of measures as set out in the 'OECD Action Plan for Youth - Giving Youth a Better Start' and developed in line with the action plan a *scoreboard for youth aged 15-24*. The OECD Action Plan for Youth proposed to:

- tackle the current youth unemployment crisis;
- tackle weak aggregate demand and boost job creation;
- provide adequate income support to unemployed youth until labour market conditions improve, but subject this to strict mutual obligations;
- maintain, and where possible expand, cost-effective active labour market measures;
- tackle demand-side barriers to the employment of low-skilled youth;
- encourage employers to continue or expand quality apprenticeship and internship programmes;
- strengthen the long-term employment prospects of youth;
- strengthen the education system and prepare all young people for the world of work;
- strengthen the role and effectiveness of vocational education and training;
- assist the transition to the world of work; and
- reshape labour market policy and institutions to facilitate access to employment and tackle social exclusion (OECD, <http://www.oecd.org/youth.htm>, 2015 [date last accessed 13 April 2015]).

The *scoreboard for youth aged 15-24*, as well as selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET), monitor youth especially in terms of labour market participation and integration, work-life balance, as well as education and training, but less on material living conditions, health, and social connectedness.¹⁰ The range of indicators is very limited and they are available for youth ages 15-24 only for the years 2001 and 2011. Moreover, as with the EU dashboard, the OECD scoreboard does not provide information on external factors and context, and, therefore can lead to misinterpretation. Additionally, the scoreboard's indicators are not disaggregated across socio-demographic characteristics to reflect the heterogeneity among youth people.

⁹ Also, a joint report by the Council and the Commission entitled 'EU Youth Report' using the dashboard indicators was issued in 2012 (European Youth Report 2012: http://ec.europa.eu/youth/library/reports/eu-youth-report-2012_en.pdf (next 2015) [date last accessed 13 April 2015]).

¹⁰ The scoreboard is available at: <http://www.oecd.org/employment/onlineoecdemploymentdatabase.htm#scoreboard> [date last accessed 13 April 2015].

c. UN indicators for the World Programme of Action for Youth

The United Nations *recommended indicators for the World Programme of Action for Youth* in 2012 (United Nations, 2012) in several dimensions, such as education, employment, poverty and hunger, health, drug abuse and juvenile delinquency, globalisation, information and communications technologies, and HIV/AIDS.¹¹ Concerning poverty and hunger, the UN suggested to list: (a) percentage of young people living in extreme poverty/below national poverty lines; (b) percentage of youth deprived of adequate shelter (each sex); (c) percentage of youth deprived of sanitation (urban and rural); and (d) percentage of youth deprived of protected water supply (urban and rural). This indicator proposal focuses on wider and more in-depth dimensions of poverty. However, those measures have not yet been transferred into indicators and made available to public.

¹¹ <http://unstats.un.org/unsd/statcom/doc12/RD-EGM-YouthIndicators.pdf> [date last accessed 13 April 2015].

Table 3.1 Overview of existing infrastructures on youth indicators and indicators suggested for IPOLIS youth module

Dimensions/Components	EU-Dashboard of Youth Indicators (definition)	IPOLIS Youth-Module (shortcut definition)	OECD Scoreboard for youth aged 15-24 & Selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET)
Material Living Conditions (EU- SOCIAL INCLUSION)			
Home ownership		Share of young people who declare to be a homeowner in relation to the total population of young people who already left home.	
At-risk-of-poverty or social exclusion	The share of young people (<18; 18-24) who are at risk of poverty and/or severely materially deprived and/or living in a household with very low work intensity compared to total population.	Share of young people (15-29) who are at risk of poverty or social exclusion in relation to the total population of the same age group.	
At-risk-of-poverty rate after social transfers	The share of young people (<18; 18-24) living in families with an equalised disposable income below 60% of the national median equalised disposable income (after social transfers) compared to total population.	Share of young people (15-29) with an equalised disposable income (after social transfer) below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold in relation to the total population of the same age group.	
Severe material deprivation	Percentage of young people (<18; 18-24) that cannot afford at least three of the following nine items: (1) to pay their rent, mortgage or utility bills; (2) to keep their home adequately warm; (3) to face unexpected expenses; (4) to eat meat or proteins regularly; (5) to go on holiday; or cannot afford to buy a: (6) TV; (7) refrigerator; (8) car; (9) telephone; compared to total population.	Share of young people (15-29) who are enforced unable to pay for at least four out of nine items in relation to the total population of the same age group.	
At-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fixed moment in time (2005)		Share of young people under 18 whose equalised disposable income in a survey year is below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold from the base year 2005 in relation to the total population of the same age group.	
Relative at risk of poverty gap by poverty threshold		The Relative at-risk-of-poverty gap displays the difference between the median equalised income of persons aged 0-17 below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold at 60% of median equalised income and the threshold itself, expressed as a percentage of the at-risk-of-poverty threshold.	

Table 3.1 Overview of Existing Infrastructures on Youth Indicators and Indicators Suggested for IPOLIS Youth Module (continued)

Dimensions/Components	EU-Dashboard of Youth Indicators (definition)	IPOLIS Youth-Module (shortcut definition)	OECD Scoreboard for youth aged 15-24 & Selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET)
Material Living Conditions (EU- SOCIAL INCLUSION)			
Persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate		Percentage of the young people (18-24) living in households where the equivalised disposable income was below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold for the current year and at least two out of the preceding three years in relation to the total population of the same age group.	
Inability of making ends meet		Proportion of young people living in a household with the ability of making ends meet with difficulty or great difficulty (EM D/GD) in relation to the total population of the same age group.	
Unmet needs for medical examination	Self-reported unmet need for medical care for young people (18-24) for the following 3 reasons: financial barriers + too far to travel + waiting times, compared to total population.	Share of young people (16-29) who declare self-reported unmet needs for medical examination because it is too expensive or too far to travel or there is a waiting list in relation to the total population of the same age group.	
Overcrowding rate		Share of young people (15-29) living in an overcrowded household in relation to the total population of the same age group.	
Housing cost overburden rate		Share of young people (15-29) living in households where the total housing costs ('net' of housing allowances) represent more than 40% of disposable income ('net' of housing allowances) in relation to the total population of the same age group.	
Severe housing deprivation		Share of young people (15-29) living in the dwelling which is considered as overcrowded, while also exhibiting at least one of the housing deprivation measures, in relation to the total population of the same age group.	

Table 3.1 Overview of Existing Infrastructures on Youth Indicators and Indicators Suggested for IPOLIS Youth Module (continued)

Dimensions/Components	EU-Dashboard of Youth Indicators (definition)	IPOLIS Youth-Module (shortcut definition)	OECD Scoreboard for youth aged 15-24 & Selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET)
Labour Market Attachment and Work-Life Balance (EU- EMPLOYMENT & ENTREPRENEURSHIP)			
Youth employment rate		Share of employed young persons (15-29) in relation to the total population of the same age group.	Employment rate (% of the age group).
Youth unemployment rate	Share of unemployed among active population (employed and unemployed) aged 15-24.	Share of young people (15-29) who are unemployed in relation to the labour force (employed and unemployed) of the total population of the same age group.	Unemployment rate (UR) (% of the labour force).
Youth long-term youth unemployment rate	Share of unemployed youth 15-24 without a job for the last 12 months or more among all unemployed in this age-group.	Share of young people (15-29) who are out of work and have been actively seeking unemployment for at least a year in relation to the total population of the same age group.	Incidence of long-term unemployment (% of unemployment).
Youth unemployment ratio	Share of unemployed among the total population (employed, unemployed and inactive), aged 15-24.		Unemployment to population ratio (% of the age group).
Relative unemployment rate			Relative unemployment rate of youth/adult (15-24)/(25-54). Relative unemployment rate low skills/high skills (ISCED<3/ISCED>3).
Youth self-employment	Percentage of self-employed among all employed aged 20-24 and 25-29.	Percentage of self-employed among all employed aged 15-29.	
Young people who would like to set up their own business	The share of young people age 15-30 answering YES to the question 'Would you like to set up your own business in the future?'		
Temporary employment rate	The share of young employed people (age 20-29) who are on a contract of limited duration.	The share of young people (15-29) who declare to be temporarily employed in relation to the total number of employees of the same age group.	

Table 3.1 Overview of Existing Infrastructures on Youth Indicators and Indicators Suggested for IPOLIS Youth Module (continued)

Dimensions/Components	EU-Dashboard of Youth Indicators (definition)	IPOLIS Youth-Module (shortcut definition)	OECD Scoreboard for youth aged 15-24 & Selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET)
<p>Working part-time or reduced hours because of caring responsibilities</p> <p>Involuntary part-time employment</p> <p>Young people not in employment, education or training (NEET)</p> <p>Living in households with very low work intensity</p> <p>Employees usually working long hours</p>	<p>Young people (age group 15-24) not in employment, nor in any education or training.</p> <p>The share of young people (<18; 18-24) who live in households with very low work intensity (households where adults worked less than 20% of their total work potential during the past year) compared to total population.</p>	<p>Working part-time or reduced hours because of caring responsibilities represent young persons (15-29) employed on a part-time basis due to looking after children or incapacitated adults as a share of all part-time employees of the same age group.</p> <p>Share young people (15-29) employed on a part-time basis as a percentage of the same age population. Persons working on an involuntary part-time basis are those who declare that they work part-time because they are unable to find full-time work.</p> <p>Share of people of age group (15-29) who is not employed and not involved in further education or training in relation to the total population of the same age group.</p> <p>Share of young people (15-29) living in a household having a work intensity below a threshold set at 0.20 in relation to all the total population of the same age group.</p> <p>Share of employees (15-29) working 40 hours or more per week in relation to all employees of the same age group.</p>	<p>Incidence of part-time work (% of employment)</p> <p>NEET rate (% of the age group).</p> <p>Breakdown in % of NEET by level of education (age 15-29).</p> <p>Maximum level of educational attainment of parents for NEETs and non-NEETs (age 15-29).</p> <p>NEET rates for women and men in % of the respective population shares (age 15-29).</p> <p>Average time spent in each activity in hours; inactive NEETs minus unemployed NEETs (age 15-29).</p>

Table 3.1 Overview of Existing Infrastructures on Youth Indicators and Indicators Suggested for IPOLIS Youth Module (continued)

Dimensions/Components	EU-Dashboard of Youth Indicators (definition)	IPOLIS Youth-Module (shortcut definition)	OECD Scoreboard for youth aged 15-24 & Selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET)
Inactive because of caring responsibilities		Share of young people (15-29) who are inactive due to caring for children or incapacitated adults in relation to all inactive people of the same age group.	
Education and Training			
Highest education attainment level: tertiary education (level 5-8)	Share of population aged 30-34 with tertiary education attainment	Share of young people (15-29) who have successfully completed tertiary education (ISCED level 5-8).	
Enrolments of the youth population in tertiary educational tracks		Share of students (15-29) enrolled in tertiary education (ISCED 5-6) refers to the count of students studying in the reference period (2004-2012) in any tertiary education programme full-time or part-time in relation to the all enrolled students at the age of 15-29.	
Non-formal education and training		Share of young people (15-29) who participated in non-formal education or training within the last four weeks before the interview in relation to the total population of the same age group.	
No longer in education or training	% of the population aged 18-24 with lower secondary education and who is no longer in education or training.	Share of early leavers from education and training aged 18-24 in relation to the total population of the same age group.	School drop-outs (% of the age group).
Low achievers	Share of 15-year olds who get a score of 1 or below (on a scale from 1 to 5) in PISA tests (Reading, Mathematics, Science).		
Young people (20-24) having completed at least upper secondary education	Percentage of young people aged 20-24 having completed at least upper secondary education (ISCED level 3c)		
Two or more foreign languages	Young people in upper secondary education (ISCED level 3 general programmes, excluding pre-vocational and vocational education) learning two or more foreign languages.	The share of young people learning two or more foreign languages in relation to the total population of enrolled young people.	

Table 3.1 Overview of Existing Infrastructures on Youth Indicators and Indicators Suggested for IPOLIS Youth Module (continued)

Dimensions/Components	EU-Dashboard of Youth Indicators (definition)	IPOLIS Youth-Module (shortcut definition)	OECD Scoreboard for youth aged 15-24 & Selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET)
Health and Risk Behaviours (EU - HEALTH & WELL-BEING)			
Long-standing illness or health problem		Share of young people (16-29) who declare to suffer from any longstanding (of a duration of at least six months) illness or health problem in relation to the total population of the same age.	
Self-perceived health		Share of young people (16-29) who perceives his/her health in general as bad or very bad in relation to all young people (16-29) answering to this question.	
Young daily smokers	Share of daily cigarette smokers in the population aged 15-24.	Share of young (15-29) people who smoke cigarettes daily in relation to the total population of young people (15-29).	
Practice of daily physical activity		Percentage of the youth population (15-34) practising at least 30 minutes of physical activity (moderate or intense) per day.	
Obesity of young people	Young people 18-24 with a Body Mass Index of 30 or above.	Share of young people (15-29) who have a BMI greater than 30 in relation to the total population of young people (15-29).	
Psychological distress	Young people (15-24) having had psychological distress during the past four weeks.	Psychological distress is based on the Mental Health Inventory (MHI-5) which consists of three depression-related items and two anxiety-related items. It has a score of 0 to 100, where a score of 100 represents optimal mental health. The indicator is presented in the form of average score.	
Hazardous alcohol consumption	Share of target group (students turning age 16 during year of ESPAD data-collection) who reported having been drunk in the last 30 days.	Share of young people (15-34) who declare to have hazardous patterns of alcohol consumption (binge drinking) daily or almost daily in relation to the total population of 15-34 year olds who declare to have an alcoholic drink more often than once a month.	
Crude death rate by suicide	Deaths caused by suicide per 100,000 inhabitants aged 15-24.	Share of young people (15-29) who commit suicide what is derived from death certificates.	
Cannabis: 12 month prevalence	Proportion of individuals aged 15-34 reporting to have used cannabis during the past 12 months.		

Table 3.1 Overview of Existing Infrastructures on Youth Indicators and Indicators Suggested for IPOLIS Youth Module (continued)

Dimensions/Components	EU-Dashboard of Youth Indicators (definition)	IPOLIS Youth-Module (shortcut definition)	OECD Scoreboard for youth aged 15-24 & Selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET)
Illicit drug use Adolescent fertility rate		Those young people (15-34 years) who report having used any medicine, resp. medicine for pain non-prescribed by a physician during the past 2 weeks are referred to in the indicator 'illicit drug use' Number of births per 1,000 women ages 15-19.	
Social Connectedness and Participation (EU-YOUTH PARTICIPATION & CONTEXT & Culture & Creativity & Volunteering & Youth and the World)			
Child population Youth population The ratio of young people in the total population Living together with parents Mean age of young people leaving the parental household Contact with relatives Single adult with children in household Youth non-voting rate	The total number of children in the age-groups 0-14 living in a member state of the European Union on January 1. The total number of young people in the age-groups 15-19, 20-24 and 25-29 living in a member state of the European Union on January 1. Young people (age-groups 15-19, 20-24 and 25-29) as a share of the total population living in a member state of the EU on January 1. Mean age of young people leaving home.	Share of young people 16-29 living in one household with their parents in relation to the total population of young people (16-29). Share of young people (16-29) who get together or have contact never or at least once a year with their relatives in relation to the total population of young people (16-29). Share of young people (15-24) living in the following type of household: single adult with children in relation to all adults with children same age group Share of young people (18-29) declaring that they did not vote at the last election in relation to the total population of that age group.	

Table 3.1 Overview of Existing Infrastructures on Youth Indicators and Indicators Suggested for IPOLIS Youth Module (continued)

Dimensions/Components	EU-Dashboard of Youth Indicators (definition)	IPOLIS Youth-Module (shortcut definition)	OECD Scoreboard for youth aged 15-24 & Selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET)
Young people's participation in political organisations/party or community/environmentally-oriented organisations	Self-reported participation in activities of a political organisation or political party or a local organisation aimed at improving their local community and/or local environment in the last 12 months. Age 15-30.		
Participation of young people in political elections at local, regional, national or EU level	Percentage of young people aged 18-30 who declare that they participated in political elections at either local, regional, national or EU level in the last three years.		
Young people 18-30 who got elected into the European Parliament	The number of young Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) elected into the European Parliament in the last elections (2009).		
Personal use of www	<p>Percentage of individuals aged 16-24 who have used the Internet, in the last 12 months for interaction with public authorities (i.e. having used the Internet for one or more of the following activities: obtaining information from public authorities web sites, downloading official forms, sending filled in forms).</p> <p>Percentage of individuals aged 16-24 declaring that they have used internet for accessing or posting opinions on websites (e.g. blogs, social networks, etc.) for discussing civic and political issues (in the last three months).</p>	Share of young people (15-29) declaring that they use the internet, the World Wide Web or e-mail - whether at home or at work - for their personal use at least once a month in relation to the total population of this age group.	
Participating in amateur artistic activities	Share of young people (15-30) who declare that they have participated in any of the following amateur artistic activities at least once in the last 12 months: Playing a musical instrument, singing, acting, dancing, writing poetry, photography, film-making.		
Participation in cultural activities	Share of young people (aged 15-30) reporting that they have participated in any of the following cultural activities in the last 12 months: visited historical monuments (palaces, castles, churches, gardens, etc.), museums or galleries, been to a cinema or a concert, a theatre, a dance performance or an opera.		

Table 3.1 Overview of Existing Infrastructures on Youth Indicators and Indicators Suggested for IPOLIS Youth Module (continued)

Dimensions/Components	EU-Dashboard of Youth Indicators (definition)	IPOLIS Youth-Module (shortcut definition)	OECD Scoreboard for youth aged 15-24 & Selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET)
<p>Participation in sports clubs, leisure time or youth clubs/organisations or cultural organisations</p> <p>Trade union membership/Young people's participation in organisations/memberships</p> <p>Occasionally unpaid voluntary work</p> <p>Trust</p>	<p>Share of young people (aged 15-30) reporting that they have participated in activities of a sports club, leisure time or youth club, any kind of youth organisation or cultural organisation in the last 12 months.</p> <p>Self-reported involvement in organised voluntary activities in the last 12 months. Age 15-30.</p> <p>Share of young people (age 15-30) declaring that they have taken part in any organised voluntary action aimed at changing something in their local community/environment during the last 12 months.</p> <p>Share of young people (age 15-30) declaring that they have stayed abroad for the purpose of volunteering.</p> <p>Share of young people (15-30) that declare having taken part in voluntary activities who have received a certificate, a diploma or other formal recognition for their participation.</p> <p>Self-reported participation in activities of an organisation active in the domain of global climate change/global warming, global development or promoting human rights in the last 12 months. Age 15-30.</p>	<p>Share of young people (15-29) who have been member of a trade union or similar organisation in the past 12 months in relation to the total population of young people (15-29).</p> <p>Share of young people (15-29) reporting at least occasionally unpaid voluntary work through the following organisations: community and social services (e.g. organisations helping the elderly, young people, disabled or other people in need); educational, cultural, sports or professional associations; Social movements (for example environmental, human rights) or charities (for example fundraising,campaigning); political parties, trade unions; other voluntary organisations.</p> <p>Share of young people (15-29) who have been member of a trade union or similar organisation in the past 12 month in relation to the total population of young people (15-29).</p>	<p>Proportion of NEET who think that most people can be trusted (age 15-29).</p>
Environmental Quality and Physical Safety			
<p>Pollution, grime or other environmental problems</p>		<p>The share of young people (15-29) living in households with reported pollution, grime or other environmental problems.</p>	
<p>Noise from neighbours or from the street</p>		<p>The share of young people (15-29) living in households with reporting noise from neighbours or from street</p>	

Table 3.1 Overview of Existing Infrastructures on Youth Indicators and Indicators Suggested for IPOLIS Youth Module (continued)

Dimensions/Components	EU-Dashboard of Youth Indicators (definition)	IPOLIS Youth-Module (shortcut definition)	OECD Scoreboard for youth aged 15-24 & Selected indicators on the situation of disadvantaged youth (NEET)
<p>Crime, violence or vandalism in the area</p> <p>Road traffic injuries: 12 month</p>	<p>Proportion of individuals aged 15-24 reporting to have had a road traffic accident, which resulted in injury for which medical treatment was sought during the past 12 months.</p>	<p>The share of young people (15-29) living in households with reported crime, violence or vandalism in the area</p> <p>Share of young people aged 15-24 reporting to have had a road traffic accident, which resulted in injury for which medical treatment was sought during the last 12 months in relation to the total population of that age group.</p>	

Source Own illustration

3.2 National initiatives (selected examples)

Additionally, several national initiatives have been set up to create infrastructures on the quality of life of youth:

- in *Finland*, two working groups undertook the task of developing a set of indicators for children (<18 years) and young people (18-29 years). Both groups have utilised pre-existing databases and proposed new indicators and statistics. The lists consist of 40-60 indicators, divided into several categories: health, education, involvement (active citizenship), employment, living environment, and support of society.
- The *Netherlands* provides a summary of information in its National Youth Monitor of the situation of populations aged 0-24 years in relation to: young people and families, health and welfare, education, employment, and justice. In total, 60 indicators are collected.¹²
- The *Swedish* National Board for Youth Affairs regularly produces a number of reports on the basis of LUPP ('local follow-up of youth policy') surveys for populations aged 13-25 years. For instance, the Youth Today (2009) - an annual compilation and analysis of 85 indicators - contains the following related policy areas: education and learning, employment and self-sufficiency, health and social exclusion, influence and representation, as well as culture and leisure.

3.3 Ongoing or newly launched projects on youth: Indicator recommendations

In addition, a cluster of five research projects on the social inclusion of young people released their findings. These five projects, include (Kutsar & Helve, 2012: 11):

- YIPPEE: 'Young people from a public care background: Pathways to education in Europe' (Denmark, Hungary, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom);
- CSEYHP: 'Combating social exclusion among young homeless populations: A comparative investigation of homeless paths among local white, local ethnic groups and migrant young men and women, and appropriate reinsertion methods' (Czech Republic, Netherlands, Portugal, United Kingdom);
- EDUMIGROM: 'Ethnic differences in education and diverging prospects for urban youth in an enlarged Europe' (Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia, Sweden, United Kingdom);
- EUMARGINS: 'On the margins of the European Community - Young adult immigrants in seven European countries' (Estonia, France, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom);
- Younex: 'Youth, unemployment, and exclusion in Europe: A multidimensional approach to understanding the conditions and prospects for social and political integration of young unemployed' (France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Sweden, Switzerland).

These projects were financed by the 'Socio-economic Sciences and Humanities' programme (SSH) of the EU's seventh framework programme for research, focusing on marginalised groups of young people and their inclusion in society. The authors recommended to '[r]educe the statistical invisibility of young people with disadvantaged backgrounds by creating EU-wide indicators (e.g. the number of young persons in public care for 12 months or more at age 16-18 years, their placement type, educational qualifications)' and to '[c]ollect comparative statistics about the situation annually at national and local levels using EU indicators and monitor the development of policies in the area; suggest improvements in the existing legal schemes' (ibid., 2012: 33). They conclude that the statistical visibility can be assured through a set of EU-wide indicators. This, however, needs to be complemented by qualitative data and knowledge building.

¹² Available at: <http://jeugdmonitor.cbs.nl/en-GB> [date last accessed 13 April 2015].

Recently a new set of initiatives and projects on youth have started, such as:

- the collaborative project ‘Strategic Transition for Youth Labour in Europe (STYLE)’ led by Professor Jacqueline O’Reilly (University of Brighton, CROME) examines ways of overcoming youth unemployment by assessing the effectiveness of labour market policies, and runs from March 2014 through September 2017 (at <http://www.style-research.eu/> [date last accessed 13 April 2015]);
- ‘Social Innovation – Empowering the Young (SociETy) for the Common Good’ lead by Professor Hans-Uwe Otto (University of Bielefeld, Bielefeld Centre for Education and Capability Research) focuses on and integrates disadvantaged young people into the research process to improve their quality of life and to foster social innovation, and runs from January 2013 through December 2015;
- the project ‘Combating Inequalities through Innovative Social Practices of and for Young People in Cities across Europe (CITISPYCE)’ builds on research that shows the disproportionate impact of the economic crisis on young people (16-24 years) across Europe. The study, lead by Jill Robinson (Aston University), is compounded by the ‘coming of age’ of the descendants of recent migrant communities who now form significant proportions of the young population in major European cities. They are Europeans in language, social habit, and cultural repertoire, yet continue to face longstanding barriers as a result of membership of communities already marginalised from mainstream labour markets and wider civic life. The project runs from January 2013 until December 2015 (at <http://www.aston.ac.uk/lss/research/research-centres/interland/citispyce/> [date last accessed 13 April 2015]);
- ‘Memory, Youth, Political Legacy and Civic Engagement (MYPLACE)’, coordinated by Professor Hilary Pilkington (University of Manchester), explores how young people’s social participation is shaped by the shadows (past, present, and future) of totalitarianism and populism in Europe. The project runs from June 2011 until May 2015 (at <http://www.fp7-myplace.eu/concept.php> [date last accessed 13 April 2015]).
- ‘Measuring Youth Well-Being (MYWeB)’ takes a balanced approach to assessing the feasibility of the European Longitudinal Study for Children and Young People (ELSCYP) through prioritising both scientific and policy imperatives. The project started in March 2014 and runs for 30 months (at <http://fp7-myweb.eu/> [date last accessed 13 April 2015]).

These initiatives and projects attempt to improve not only upon knowledge on existing indicators and theory, but also push indicator- and knowledge-building via qualitative data.

4. Overview of dataset infrastructure

In this chapter, we take an inventory of data sources that may serve as an infrastructure for building and sustaining the youth module of IPOLIS. We consider cross-country comparative surveys that are either conducted on samples representing the total population living in individual households or only youth. Datasets which span over the whole time period of 2004 till 2013 and cover the entire population are preferred.

The main data sources used for the IPOLIS youth module are part of the European Statistical System (ESS): the European Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS), the EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC), the UNESCO/OECD/EUROSTAT (UOE) data collection on education, and the European Health Interview Survey (EHIS). Additionally, data from the European Social Survey (ESS) as well as from the European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction (EMCDDA), the World Development Indicators (WDI – The World Bank), and the World Health Organisation Causes of Death (COD – WHO) were consulted for building the IPOLIS youth module (Table 4.1).

As Table 4.1. shows, for the domain ‘*Material living conditions*’ we use the EU-SILC dataset because it includes questions for indicator building in all recommended subdomains such as poverty, material deprivation, and housing. Additionally, the dataset covers the relevant timespan and the scope of EU countries. Due to the yearly frequency of the survey, the EU-SILC is sustainably useful for the IPOLIS databases (on methodological issues see European Union, 2010; European Commission, 2010a; European Union, 2013c; European Commission/Eurostat, 2014).

The domain ‘*Labour market attachment and work-life balance*’ contains labour market issues about employment and work-life balance. This range of topics is widely covered by the EU-LFS dataset, which also includes the required timespan and country coverage, and is conducted at least yearly. In this domain, only the indicator ‘employees usually working long hours’ is taken from another database (OECD collection) since the EU-LFS does not provide an indicator addressing long or overtime working hours (on methodological issues see European Union, 2013b, 2014b, c).

The domain ‘*Education and training*’ contains mainly indicators based on the EU-LFS dataset since educational attainment, lifelong learning, and early school leaving are very well covered. Only information about enrolment in tertiary education and achievement in basic skills (learning two or more foreign languages) has to be gained from other datasets, namely the UOE.

The domain ‘*Health and risk behaviours*’ comprises information from several datasets since there was no one comprehensive dataset. Health status is covered by information from the EU-SILC since this dataset contains information about health status and shows the widest timespan and country coverage. Regarding health behaviour, EHIS, in addition to EMCDDA for drug use, WDI for teenage pregnancy, and COD for suicide, are used for covering this subdomain. The EHIS dataset is used although it provides information on only one year (2008) of the relevant timespan, because it covers youth relevant health factors, such as obesity, smoking, and alcohol consumption for the relevant age group of 15-29 year olds. Moreover, the EHIS survey is conducted every five years and provides therefore sustainable, even if temporally separated measures for the IPOLIS database. EHIS data is also used for the component of physical safety in the domain ‘*Environmental quality and physical safety*’ (on methodological issues see European Union, 2013a). However, this

domain is based mainly on data from EU-SILC. EU-SILC asks not only whether the household's accommodation has 'any pollution, grime or other environmental problem caused by traffic or industry' and about noise from neighbours or from the street (of traffic, business, factories, etc.) but also whether the household reference persons have experiences of violent crime in the area.

The first component of family and peer relationships in the domain '*Social connectedness and civic participation*' uses information from the EU-SILC and EU-LFS datasets. Concerning the second component of civic participation, information about each and every subcomponent is provided by the ESS dataset, which covers a wide timespan and country coverage like the EU-SILC and EU-LFS, but is conducted only every second year (on methodological issues see European Social Survey, 2012). For volunteering however we use information from European Quality of Life Surveys (EQLS).

All other datasets listed in Table 4.1, such as Flash Eurobarometer and Adult Education Survey, are not used for IPOLIS youth module because only single years or relatively few countries are covered by the surveys or only certain age groups are covered.

Table 4.1 Overview of Data Sources for Youth Module of IPOLIS

Name of micro-dataset	Abbreviation and years available	Countries available	Sample size and coverage, access	Use for which domains and components?
Labour Force Survey	EU-LFS 2013 release (1983-2012).	28 Member states - IS-NO-CH (DE from 2002 onwards, MT from 2009 onwards) specific household data for DK (2002-2012), FI (2003-2012) and SE (2009-2012).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Persons aged 15 years and over living in private households. - Sample size across the EU: about 1.5 millions of individuals. - Access via Eurostat. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 (Labour Market Attachment and Work Life Balance). 3 (Education and Training). 5 (Social connectedness and participation).
European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions	EU-SILC 2013/14 release (2003-2012/13).	EU27 + Norway, Iceland, Turkey, Croatia, Switzerland Three further countries (Montenegro, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia (FYROM) and Serbia) are in test implementation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Persons aged 16 years and over living in private households. - Sample size across the EU: 292,150 individuals living in 141,000 private households (EC/Eurostat, 2014). - Access via Eurostat. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 (Material Living Conditions). 4 (Health and Risk Behaviours). 5 (Social connectedness and participation). 6 (Environmental quality and physical safety).
Labour Force Statistics in OECD Countries based on national LFS	OECD collection/LFS (different national survey periods).	OECD countries (incl. EU28).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National LFS differ along coverage and timing of the survey (see http://www.oecd.org/els/emp/LFSNO_TES_SOURCES.pdf [date last accessed 13 April 2015]). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 (Labour Market Attachment and Work Life Balance).
UNESCO-OECD-Eurostat (UOE) data collection on education statistics	UOE (1998-2014).	27 EU Member States, EFTA/EEA countries, the candidate countries, South-East European countries, OECD Member States situated outside Europe, other countries (e.g. Israel).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enrolments in studies of foreign languages. - Access via OECD. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 (Education and Training).
European Social Survey	ESS (2002, 2004, 2006, 2010, 2012).	2002: EU15, 2004: EU15, 2006: EU25, 2008: EU28, 2010 EU28, 2012: EU28 + Albania, Iceland, Israel, Kosovo, Norway, Russian Federation, Turkey.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Representative sample of all persons aged 15 and over resident within private households. - Minimum 'effective achieved sample size' of 1,500 or 800 in countries with ESS populations of less than 2 million. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 (Social connectedness and participation).
Causes of death	COD (from 1994 onwards (Belgium, Germany: 1992, Ireland: 1993, Bulgaria: 1995, Latvia, Slovakia: 1996, Cyprus, Poland, Romania: 1999, Liechtenstein: 2010 onwards)).	EU28, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Albania, Iceland, Norway, Liechtenstein and Switzerland.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Based on the information provided on death certificates (administrative data). - All deaths of residents and non-residents are counted. - Access via Eurostat. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4 (Health and Risk Behaviours).

Table 4.1 Overview of Data Sources for Youth Module of IPOLIS (continued)

Name of micro-dataset	Abbreviation and years available	Countries available	Sample size and coverage, access	Use for which domains and components?
World Development Indicators	WDI (1980-2012).	Worldwide.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Based on data on registered live births from vital registration systems or, in the absence of such systems, from censuses or sample surveys. - Access via The World Bank – World DataBank. 	4 (Health and Risk Behaviours).
European Health Interview Survey	EHIS 1 (2006-2009). EHIS 2 (expected 2014).	EHIS 1 EU17. EHIS 2 EU28.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Population aged at least 15 and living in private households. - Sample size wave 2: 210,000 individuals. - Access via Eurostat. 	4 (Health and Risk Behaviours). 6 (Environmental Quality and Physical Safety).
European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction	EMCDDA Data Collection (2007-2012, several years for different countries).	EU28.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview of national surveys. 	4 (Health and Risk Behaviours).
European Quality of Life Surveys	EQLS	<p>Second EQLS in 2007-2008 - 31 countries: 27 EU Member States, Croatia, FYR Macedonia, Turkey and Norway.</p> <p>Third EQLS in 2011-2012 - 34 countries: 27 EU Member States and Croatia, Iceland, FYR Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Turkey and Kosovo.</p>	The target population is all residents of the countries mentioned above, aged 18 or older.	5 (Social connectedness and participation).
Adult Education Survey	AES 2007, 2011 (next expected in 2016).	29 (30 in 2011) countries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Population aged 25 to 64. - Total net sample size: 183,000 persons in 2007 (225,000 in 2011). 	Not used for IPOLIS youth module: not the whole age range, only two years covered.
Flash Eurobarometer	Flash Eurobarometer N 375 ‘European Youth: Participation in Democratic Life’ (26 January and 4 February 2011).	EU27 Member States, Croatia, Iceland, Norway and Turkey	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Persons aged 15-35 years (section: youth participation - young people aged 15-30). - Total net sample size: 57,000 young Europeans were interviewed by telephone. 	Not used for IPOLIS youth module: only one year covered
	Flash Eurobarometer N 158 ‘Young people and drugs’ (2004). Flash Eurobarometer N 233 ‘Young people and drugs’ (2008). Flash Eurobarometer N 330 ‘Youth attitudes on drugs’ (9 and 13 May 2011)	EU27	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young people aged 15-24. - Total net sample size: over 12,000 young Europeans were interviewed by telephone. 	Not used for IPOLIS youth module: only three years covered, not whole age range

Source Own collection of information from different datasets and data collections

5. From six domains to 15 components to 33 sub-components to 49 indicators: the proposed structure of the IPOLIS youth module

This chapter aims at providing the methodological underpinnings of the selection of indicators measuring the different aspects of youth's quality of life. The chapter is organised according to the domains and components/subcomponents of IPOLIS. However, only those domains and sub-components of IPOLIS are discussed here which are relevant for youth and contain indicators.

The indicators identified in this report fall into 14 components reflecting general characteristics that have been considered as important elements of well-being (Gábos & Kopasz, 2014). The six domains are: (a) material living conditions; (b) labour market attachment and work-life balance; (c) education and training; (d) health and risk behaviours; (e) social connectedness and civic participation; and (f) environmental quality and physical safety. These are complemented by two dimensions that summarise key aspects of the economic, social, and policy context. However, these two dimensions are dealt with in a separate report.

The indicators suggested below thus fall into the following 33 subcomponents (Table 5.1). Components and subcomponents that are marked in light grey are not part of the IPOLIS youth module, but are rather part of the general framework of IPOLIS.

Table 5.1 Proposed Structure of IPOLIS Youth Module and Deviations from IPOLIS Overall Structure

Domain	Component	Subcomponent
1. Material living conditions	1.1 Poverty	a. Extent of poverty b. Depth of poverty c. Persistence of poverty
	1.2 Material deprivation	
	1.3 Housing	a. Overcrowding b. Housing costs c. Housing deprivation
	1.4 Poverty and social exclusion (EU 2020)	
2. Labour market attachment and work-life balance	2.1 Labour market attachment	a. Employment b. Precarious employment c. Self-employment d. Unemployment e. Labour market attachment of households
	2.2 Work-life balance	a. Work and leisure b. Work and care
3. Education and training	3.1 Access to and quality of education	a. Early childhood education b. Educational attainment c. Lifelong learning
	3.2 Educational achievement	a. Achievement in basic skills b. Early school leaving
4. Health and risk behaviours	4.1 Health status	a. Objective health status b. Subjective health status
	4.2 Health behaviours	a. Physical activity b. Obesity
	4.3 Risk behaviours	a. Smoking b. Alcohol consumption c. Illicit drugs d. Teenage births/Pregnancy e. Psychological distress f. Suicide g. Bullying (+ fighting)
5. Social connectedness and CIVIC participation	5.1 Family and peer relationships	a. Family relationships b. Peer relationships
	5.2 Civic participation	a. Voting/Voter turnout b. Volunteering c. Group membership d. Internet use
6. Environmental quality and physical safety	6.1 Environmental quality	a. Outside air pollution b. Noise
	6.2 Physical safety	

* Light grey – not part of the IPOLIS youth module.
Source Gábos and Kopasz, 2014: 20, 30-35; own adaptations

5.1 Period and sample coverage

Overall, the proposed infrastructure follows from the aim that indicators should: make use of existing information; be relevant in the corresponding domain; be compiled in a simple framework; be specific with little room for (mis-)interpretation; be continuously updated,; and be accessible (on indicator-based assessment see European Union, 2014a).

All indicators cover *all countries of the EU28* (for exceptions see Chapter 6). Additionally, aggregated information for the EU28, EU27, EU15, and EU12 are provided. For all indicators, the time period *from 2004 until 2013* is covered where possible.

5.2 Defining ‘youth’ and age bands

The *definition of youth* is problematic. Sociologists have long argued that ‘youth’ is socially constructed rather than biologically determined (Williamson, 2002). According to demographers, the nature of youth is changing under pressure from economic and sociocultural factors. Thus, the ‘traditional’ age boundaries of youth - 15-24 years - are becoming more blurred and extended. So there is a rationale to look at youth transition as a broader and seamless process from early adolescence to post-adolescence. However, there are two challenges for this concept: (a) for policy to differentiate between measures for ‘early adolescents’, ‘adolescents’ and ‘post-adolescents’ and to ensure ‘seamless transitions’ between the phases (Williamson, 2002: 32); and (b) for measurement to define corresponding bands, and to sample and generate indicators accordingly.

Former initiatives, such as the EU Youth Strategy, do not operate with an official definition for the specific period in life when a person is considered to be ‘young’. The definition of ‘youth’ varies from one member state to another and the age under consideration differs with time and socio-economic development. The white paper ‘*A New Impetus for European Youth*’ states: ‘Youth is regarded here as the period from 15 to 25 years of age’ (European Commission, 2001: 6/FN1), while the ‘Youth in Action programme 2010-2013’ targets young people between 13-30 years (European Commission, 2006:9),¹³ the EU dashboard of youth indicators covers the age range 15-34 years (see Chapter 3; European Commission, 2011: 2), the ‘Youth on the Move’ programme target group is 15-30 years, and finally the ‘Erasmus+’ programme target group is 13-30 years (European Commission, 2013d: 56/13).¹⁴

The applied concept for the IPOLIS youth module concentrates on the *age range 15 to 29 years* and differentiates between the life phases and corresponding transition issues within the age band as illustrated in Table 5.2 below. The categories are not strictly separated but rather overlap, change over time, and are different across cultures. However, *age bands of indicators range from 15 to 19 years, 20 to 24 years, and 25 to 29 years* where possible. If those age bands are not applied, the indicators refer to the *main ‘adolescence’ phase between ages 18 to 24 years*. This is also a vulnerable period with risks related to substance misuse, risky social behaviour, difficulties with social relations, unsuccessful career choices, unemployment, and poverty.

Table 5.2 Youth age bands, transition phases, and transition issues

Growth phase	Early adolescence 15/16 – 19 years	Adolescence 20 – 24 years 18 – 24 years	Late adolescence 25 – 29 years
Transition issues	Early prevention of social risks	- Life management - Labour market integration - Risk prevention, harm reduction	- Independence - Facility formation - Labour market stabilisation

Source Siurala, 2006: 10, own adaptations

The breakdowns for the age groups sometimes vary depending on the indicator. As stated above, the very heterogeneous population results in the fact that not all indicators are appropriate for each age group. For instance, home ownership or voting turnout are not appropriate for the youth population under 18 years.

¹³ Page 9 Article 2 ‘Without prejudice to the arrangements in the Annex for the implementation of actions, the Programme is intended for young people aged between 15 to 28, although certain actions are open to young people aged as young as 13 or up to the age of 30.’ (at <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02006D1719-20061214&rid=7> [date last accessed 13 April 2015]).

¹⁴ The ‘ProYouth’ initiative promotes healthy eating, body satisfaction, and preventing eating disorders for young people aged 15 to 25.

Based on theoretical considerations as well as empirical evidence, we attempt to select the most appropriate indicators for each domain and subcomponents. Table 5.2 summarises the selected indicators along domains and (sub)components.

5.3 Indicators in the domain 'Material living conditions'

The first domain '*Material living conditions*' describes standards of living as an aspect of the quality of life concept. The measurement of material living conditions can be accomplished through monetary or non-monetary measures (e.g. income or access to material goods) (Boarini & d'Ercole, 2006; European Commission, 2012; OECD, 2013). The following four components claim to satisfy the multidimensional nature of the concept of material living conditions.

Within the domain, the first component '*Poverty*' describes the lack of monetary and material resources, as well as low work intensity in young people's households at a given point in time, but also incorporates terms of change and persistence. According to the widely known concepts of poverty (European Commission, 2012), the component is split into the subcomponents 'Extent of poverty', 'Depth of poverty', and 'Persistency of poverty'. The first subcomponent contains the indicators 'At-risk-of-poverty after social transfers' and 'At-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fixed moment in time (2005)'. The first indicator has a narrow focus on the lack of monetary resources in describing those at risk of poverty in terms of: having an equivalised disposable income below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold of 60% of the national median of equivalised disposable income after social transfers. Thus, this indicator focuses not only on household resources but also on the redistribution of the welfare state. The latter indicator was selected to describe longer periods of monetary poverty since its conception allows for the control of sudden fluctuations in poverty thresholds over time by keeping the poverty threshold fixed. The second component includes the indicator 'Relative at-risk-of-poverty gap by poverty threshold' as a measure of depth of poverty. The third component focuses on the persistence of poverty, thus accounting for longer poverty periods and ignoring shorter periods of poverty (Özdemir & Ward, 2010). The indicator 'Persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate' shows those groups of the youth population who are at risk of poverty at least two out of three years in a row. This concept provides a means of distinguishing between those with low-income levels over the long-term and those for whom income below the poverty threshold is merely transitory.

The concept of material deprivation is addressed within the second component '*Material deprivation*'. This component refers to non-monetary measures of the lack of material goods, financial strains, and inability to live an adequate life (Boarini & d'Ercole, 2006; European Commission, 2012). The indicator 'Severe material deprivation' defines young people who are unable to pay for at least four out of nine items related to housing conditions and equipment, as well as vacation and nutrition issues. As another aspect of material deprivation, we selected the indicator 'Unmet needs for medical examination', which covers missed medical examinations due to high cost of expenses, long travel distances, or long waiting lists. Hence, this indicator constitutes an important aspect of material deprivation, since it deals with a necessary item of everyday life. The third indicator in the second component is 'Inability of making ends meet'. The objective of the indicator on 'Inability of making ends meet' is to assess the respondent subjective feeling about the level of difficulty experienced by the household in making ends meet.¹⁵ Its assessment is based on the household's total net income (with all income sources are to be taken into account and that several household member

¹⁵ The formal question in the household data file is: 'A household may have different sources of income and more than one household member may contribute to it. Thinking of your household's total income, is your household able to make ends meet, namely, to pay for its usual necessary expenses?' Answer categories on a six-category scale: 1 - with great difficulty, 6 - very easily.

may contribute to the total income). Overall the indicator reflects not only the level of material resources a household possesses, but also its adequacy to ensure a decent standard of living.

The third component, '*Housing*', presents living conditions of young people related to their housing situation, such as overcrowding, housing costs, and housing deprivation. According to this indicator, housing also concerns unmet general living standards (European Commission, 2012). The component is structured into the three above-mentioned subcomponents. The first deals with the 'Overcrowding rate', which describes the relationship between the number of rooms within the dwelling and the number of household members. The 'Housing cost overburden rate' covers the subcomponent 'Housing costs' and defines young people who have a financial burden due to high housing costs in relation to their disposable income. This subcomponent also includes the indicator 'Home ownership' to cover non-monetary aspects of wealth. This indicator is applied only for those groups who have already left their parents' home. All other cases potentially mix up non-monetary wealth of (grand)parents and children. The indicator 'Severe housing deprivation' combines young people living in an overcrowded dwelling and additionally exhibiting at least one of the housing deprivation measures.

The last component in this domain, '*Poverty and social exclusion (EU2020)*', refers to head indicators in the European Commission's monitoring process. Three indicators have been published in order to monitor and document whether the following EU-target has been reached: poverty should be reduced by lifting at least 20 million people out of the risk of poverty or social exclusion. The following three indicators: 'People living in households with very low work intensity', 'People at risk of poverty after social transfers', and 'People severely materially deprived' add up to one overriding indicator of 'People at risk of poverty or social exclusion'. Thus, at least one of the following conditions: (a) being at risk of poverty; (b) being severely materially deprived; and/or (c) living in a household with very low work intensity, are covered by this indicator at the level of the young person's household.

5.4 Indicators in the domain 'Labour market attachment and work-life balance'

The domain '*Labour market attachment and work-life balance*' refers to the lack of labour market integration and participation, as well tensions between labour market integration and reproductive tasks (i.e. care) in terms of quality of life for young people. Integration and participation in the labour market is necessary for assuring a livelihood and building up independent households and lives (OECD, 2013; European Commission, 2012). This domain includes indicators referring to one of the core objectives of the EU Youth Strategy (see Chapter 2), that is providing more and equal opportunities for young people in education and in the job market.

The component '*Labour market attachment*' covers the subcomponents 'Employment', 'Precarious employment', 'Self-employment', and 'Unemployment and labour market attachment of households'. Employment is perceived by many EU states as a key factor of social inclusion and offers the most important means of escaping the poverty cycle. Being employed and earning wages is crucial for economic independence; therefore, those events that may lead young adults of working age to interrupt their working lives or not to participate in the labour market can generate a potential risk of poverty. The subcomponent 'Employment' includes the 'Youth employment rate' as an objective indicator providing an overview of the general participation of young people in the labour market. The subcomponent 'Precarious employment' comprises both 'Temporary employment rate' due to limited contracts and 'Involuntary part-time employment' due to childcare or other family responsibilities. This subcomponent represents the group of the precariously employed youth among the employed. Therefore, the indicator can provide both information about first steps in

accessing the labour market and offers a glance at unstable employment situations of young people. Both indicators are objective and highly relevant for targeting young people's labour market attachment. The third subcomponent 'Self-employment' includes the indicator 'Youth self-employment', which refers to the 'percentage of self-employed among all employed aged 15-29'. Since unemployment is a relevant issue in the labour market attachment of the youth population, the fourth subcomponent addresses 'Unemployment'. This subcomponent contains three indicators: the 'Youth unemployment rate', the 'Youth long-term unemployment rate', and the 'Not in employment and not in any education and training rate (NEET)'. The youth unemployment rate indicates the general characteristic of unemployed young people, which becomes more and more relevant due to the financial and economic crisis and the EU Youth Strategy to support young people's integration into the labour market. The youth long-term unemployment rate serves as an indicator of the persistence of unemployment and represents the group of young people who have entered long-term unemployment in the early working life years and have few chances of getting into a stable employment in the future. The NEET rate points to young people who are unemployed or inactive and not in any formal or non-formal education or training. This group of young people shows a high risk of labour market and social exclusion and therefore also a high risk for poverty. The last subcomponent, 'Labour market attachment of households', is covered by the indicator 'Household with very low work intensity', meaning households where all members of working age worked less than 20% of their total work potential during the previous 12 months. This low work intensity, again, indicates an unstable participation in the labour market and moreover a high risk of poverty and social exclusion.

The second component addresses 'Work-life balance' since the compatibility of family and work is an important issue, especially regarding the increasing employment of women. The interruption of working life or inactivity for family care reasons may generate a loss of economic independence and, later in the life cycle, a lower level of social protection (lower pensions). The first subcomponent 'Work and leisure' includes one indicator referring to the working time of employees. The indicator 'Employees usually working long hours' gives an overview of the share of young people who need to work 40 hours or more. Those young people could suffer from a poor work-life balance. The second subcomponent, 'Work and care', includes two indicators: 'Working part-time or reduced hours because of caring responsibilities', describes young people who decide to work part-time on a voluntary basis due to looking after children or incapacitated adults. This group of young people might have a higher risk of poverty and social exclusion (as well as low pensions) based on their decreased income. And, 'Inactive because of caring responsibilities' representing young people who are inactive due to caring for children or incapacitated adults.

5.5 Indicators in the domain 'Education and training'

The domain '*Education and training*' relates also to the EU Youth Strategy target to support the accessibility to education and training at all levels, as well as the opportunity for lifelong learning for young people (European Commission, 2011). Both access to education and training, as well as lifelong learning, could facilitate the achievement of other economic and non-economic outcomes (OECD, 2013: 23, 184f.), for example the entrance into the labour market. Hence, education addresses youth unemployment and reduces the risk of poverty and social exclusion. This domain consists of two components.

The first component '*Access to and quality of education*' is divided into the subcomponents educational attainment and lifelong learning. The subcomponent 'Highest educational attainment level: Tertiary education (level 5-8)' provides an overview of the youth population which has successfully completed the following levels of educational attainment: (a) ISCED level 5 - short-cycle tertiary educa-

tion, (b) ISCED level 6 - bachelor's or equivalent level, (c) ISCED level 7 - master's or equivalent level and (d) ISCED level 8 - doctoral or equivalent level. The second indicator of this subcomponent shows the *'Enrolments of the youth population in tertiary educational tracks'*. This is of particular interest since the enhancement of the tertiary educational attainment is important when considering the promotion of employability of youth. The subcomponent 'Lifelong learning' is described by the indicator 'Non-formal education and training'. The participation of young people in non-formal education and training might increase their employability and thus decrease their risk of poverty and social exclusion.

The second component, *'Educational achievement'*, is split into the subcomponents 'Achievement in basic skills' and 'Early school leaving'. The first subcomponent includes an indicator representing the share of young people who are 'Learning two or more foreign languages'. The second subcomponent addresses early school leaving with the indicator 'No longer in education or training', which indicates the youth population which has finished a lower secondary education at most and are no longer involved in education or training. This population is not able to enter the labour market, further vocational education or training, or higher education, and hence has a high risk of poverty and social exclusion.

5.6 Indicators in the domain 'Health and risk behaviours'

The domain *'Health and risk behaviours'* refers to the support of young people's health and well-being. Health is not only intrinsically relevant for an individual's quality of life, but also enables an individual's participation in social activities and therefore social inclusion (OECD, 2013: 23; European Commission, 2012). According to the EU Youth Strategy, they 'focus on the promotion of mental and sexual health, sport, physical activity and healthy life styles as well as the prevention and treatment of injury, eating disorders, addictions and substance abuse' (European Commission, 2011: 7). The domain is structured into the following three components.

The first component, *'Health status'*, includes information about the objective and subjective health status, split into two separate indicators. The objective health status is measured by the subjective declaration of the respondents that they suffer from any 'Longstanding illness or health problem'. Here, only the duration of the illness (at least six months), but not the type of illness, is specified. In contrast, the subjective health status indicator 'self-perceived health' is operationalised by the subjective perception of general health as bad or very bad for youth aged 16-29 years old.

The second component, *'Health behaviours'*, contains two subcomponents and two indicators. The first component 'Physical activity' includes the indicator 'Practice of daily physical activity' which measures practising at least 30 minutes of physical activity (moderate or intense) per day for young people age 15-34. Recommended by the WHO - at least 60 minutes per day - participation in physical activity can assist in the social development of young people by providing opportunities for self-expression, building self-confidence, social interaction and integration. Similarly, it also has psychological benefits in young people by improving their control over symptoms of anxiety and depression. The health behaviour related to the second component 'obesity' measured by the indicator 'Obesity of young people' is an ever growing problem and especially occurs in young populations (EU Action Plan on Childhood Obesity, 2014-2020; 2014d). The obesity of the youth population is measured through the body mass index of young people aged 15-29 years.

The third component, *'Risk behaviour'*, consists of six subcomponents addressing youth-relevant risk behaviours, such as 'Smoking, alcohol consumption, illicit drug use, teenage pregnancy, psychological distress and suicide'. The corresponding indicators, except for suicide, are highly relevant for

targeting risk behaviours in the youth population. Furthermore, they correspond with the EU Youth Strategy aspects of mental and sexual health, healthy lifestyles, eating disorders, addictions, and substance abuse (European Commission, 2011). The indicator ‘Young daily smokers’ refers to the share of 15-29 years old who smoke cigarettes daily. The indicator ‘Hazardous alcohol consumption’ shows the share of young people (15-34 years) who declare binge drinking on an (almost) daily basis in relation to the population of 15-32 year olds who declare to have an alcoholic drink more often than once a month. Those young people (15-34 years) who report having used any medicine, resp. medicine for pain non-prescribed by a physician during the past two weeks are referred to in the indicator ‘Illicit drug use’. Furthermore, teenage pregnancy is indicated by the ‘Adolescent fertility rate’, which is the number of births per 1,000 women ages 15-19 years. One of the future problems in terms of health might be psychological distress. We include an indicator on ‘Psychological distress’ based on the Mental Health Inventory Index. The last indicator in this component is the ‘Crude death rate by suicide’. It describes the crude death rate of 15-29 year olds in relation to the total population.

5.7 Indicators in the domain ‘Social connectedness and civic participation’

The domain ‘*Social connectedness and civic participation*’ refers to the embeddedness in social networks and social activity of the youth population. This is the second objective of the EU Youth Strategy (see Chapter 2). Social connectedness is a considerable part of an individual’s quality of life since they can use their network resources for their own purposes, for instance finding a job, receiving support in times of need, or drawing on presence of companions in distress (OECD, 2013: 23, 187f.). Moreover, civic participation is a sign of involvement in, and contribution to, political decisions which also influence their own lives (*ibid*). Regarding this, the domain is split into two components, ‘*Family and peer relationships*’ and ‘*Civic participation*’.

The first subcomponent, ‘*Family relationships*’, describes the housing situation and contact frequency of young people with their relatives. The indicator ‘Living together with parents’ describes the group of the youth population which is still living together with their parents in one household. With regards to the very heterogeneous population of youth, this indicator is highly relevant, dividing the youth who have already left the parental home from those who still live in the parental home. This will further influence measures of household income or expenses. In contrast, the second indicator ‘Contact with relatives’ differentiates the group of young people who get together regularly with their parents from those who have very little contact with them. The third indicator, ‘Single adult with children in household’, highlights the distribution of the youth population in lone parent households among all adults aged 15-24 with children. Considering that this particular household type is thought to be accompanied by a lower quality of life, this distribution is important for targeting youth.

The second, third, and fourth subcomponents cover the political and non-political involvement of young people, with a focus on voting turnout related to political participation, and group membership and internet use related to non-political participation. The first subcomponent, ‘Voting/Voter turnout’ describes the indicator ‘Youth non-voting rate’ as the portion of the youth population (18-29 years) which did not vote during the last political elections. This indicator is selected for young people who are at least 18 years old, because at this age we assume that they are old enough to be entitled to vote.

The second subcomponent, ‘volunteering’, covers unpaid work for social or political organisations. The corresponding indicator ‘Occasionally unpaid voluntary work’ shows the share of young people (15-29) reporting occasionally unpaid voluntary work through the following organisations:

- community and social services (e.g. organisations helping the elderly, young people, disabled or other people in need);
- educational, cultural, sports or professional associations;
- social movements (for example environmental, human rights) or charities (for example fundraising, campaigning);
- political parties, trade unions;
- other voluntary organisations;

The third subcomponent, 'Group membership', addresses the membership in different groups or organisations, for example environmental organisations or other groups targeting societal issues. The corresponding indicator, 'Trade union membership: past 12 months', represents the trade union membership of the youth population (15-29 years) as a sign of involvement in civic engagement. The last subcomponent 'Internet use' refers to the participation of young people in digital media as a relevant component of participation in everyday life, especially for the youth population. The indicator 'Personal use of www' gives an overview of the portion of the youth population (15-29 years) which uses the internet for personal use.

5.8 Indicators in the domain 'Environmental quality and physical safety'

The last domain 'Environmental quality and physical safety' relates to the neighbourhood situation of the youth population. The importance of the environmental quality of neighbourhoods is related to individuals' general health situation, as well as to the facilitation of general activities taking place in the neighbourhood (OECD, 2013: 23). This concept is more related to an area than to an individual. To measure the presence of environmental problems in the immediate neighbourhood we include two indicators: one for measuring the percentage of young people living in households that reported noise from neighbours or from the street 'Noise from neighbours or from the street', and one for measuring the percentage of young people living in households that reported any pollution, grime or other environmental problem caused by traffic or industry called 'Pollution, grime or other environmental problems' Furthermore, the second component 'physical safety' is related to health in general, but also to unburdened living in one's neighbourhood. The indicator 'Crime, violence or vandalism in the area' measures the share of young people (15-29) living in households with reported crime, violence or vandalism in the area. Moreover, road traffic injuries play a big role in the lives of youth. On the one hand, they can be affected by the juvenility of others and be a victim of road traffic injuries caused by others. On the other hand, they themselves can be the cause of road traffic injuries and injure themselves and/or others. This is why we chose the indicator 'Road traffic injuries: 12 months' for people ages 15-24 years who had an accident within the last 12 months.

5.9 Disaggregation of indicators: Breakdowns

Many components of the concept of poverty and living conditions operate differently for men and women (Elder & Johnson, 1999: 448). For example, labour market participation and work-life balance are major issues affecting more women than men, since in most countries women are still concerned with caring for children or family responsibilities (*ibid.*). The same holds for individual earnings. If women are employed, they earn significantly less than their male colleagues. Therefore, women are at higher risk of poverty and social exclusion than males. Furthermore, some of the risk behaviours operate differently for men and women. While men show more delinquent risk behaviours, physical inactivity and cigarette smoking have a higher prevalence among women (MacArthur *et al.*, 2012). Since many of our proposed indicators generate different outcomes for men and women, nearly every indicator has been disaggregated by *sex*.

Several studies have shown that migrants are often at higher risk of poverty and have lower chances of participating in the labour market (Lelkes & Zolyomi, 2011). Hence, we selected the breakdown *country of birth* to differentiate between the population which was born in the reporting country and the population which was born in a foreign country.

As we know from academic research, more life-changing transitions occur during the young adult years than at any other time in people's lives (Iacovou, 2010). Those transitions display an ambiguity between independence (forming an independent household) and dependency (sharing resources with parents) (Iacovou, 2011). The impact of those transformative transitions on standard of living and quality of life is tremendous, with young people forming economically independent households (Aassve *et al.*, 2007; Iacovou, 2009). However, problematic circumstances in terms of standards of living and quality of life have an impact on transitions and independence. For instance, the high levels of unemployment or precarious employment among young people, or the low wages that young people receive when employed, have led them to remain longer in the parental home or even return to the parental home. Accordingly, indicators have been disaggregated by *household status*, either: (a) a person living with parents, or (b) a person not living with parents where possible.

Some of the indicator outcomes differ due to financial issues, such as income or poverty status. The affected indicators are especially those dealing with material deprivation and housing, since those issues are strongly correlated with financial resources. Additionally, most of the indicators describing health status, health behaviour, and risk behaviour are deeply related to monetary capabilities. Accordingly, we disaggregated the above-mentioned indicators by the breakdowns of *income quintiles* or *poverty status*, either below or above the poverty level.

For other indicators, it is reasonable to differentiate between different labour market statuses. Regarding the indicator, 'Not in employment and not in any education and training rate (NEET)', it makes sense to differentiate *activity status*, in other words to differentiate between the unemployed population which is searching for employment, and the inactive population which is not part of the labour force and is neither employed nor unemployed. In fact, the inactive population is not searching for any employment for several reasons, for example, because they are still in school or university, or are housewives; whereas the unemployed population is indeed searching for employment. Furthermore, with regards to the work-life balance, we divide the *employment status* in terms of self-employment and dependent employment. Since self-employed individuals are known for longer working hours, we disaggregated the indicator 'Employees usually working long hours' by employment status. The indicator 'No longer in education or training' has been disaggregated by *labour status*. This enables the differentiation between early school leavers who are either employed or unemployed.

Research has shown that a correlation exists between labour market participation and education, in this sense, higher education leads to better labour market participation (OECD, 2011). Therefore, it is necessary to disaggregate labour market attachment indicators, such as employment, self-employment, unemployment, or NEET, by *educational levels*. Education is usually measured by International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) levels, where lower ISCED levels indicate less education. Moreover, education is expected to influence health behaviour in a positive way. Accordingly, the health indicator would be ideally disaggregated by education as well. However, within the health domain there is only one disaggregation due to educational level provided for 'Hazardous alcohol consumption'.

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
1. Material living conditions							
1.1 Poverty							
<i>a. Extent of poverty</i>							
At risk of poverty after social transfers	1.1.1	Yes	The at-risk-of-poverty rate is the share of young people (15-29) with an equivalised disposable income (after social transfer) below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold in relation to the total population of the same age group. The at-risk-of-poverty threshold is set at 60 % of the national median equivalised disposable income after social transfers. This indicator does not measure wealth or poverty, but low income in comparison to other residents in that country, which does not necessarily imply a low standard of living.	Sex, age groups a), country of birth, household status	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2005: 30; from 2010: 29
At-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fixed moment in time (2005)	1.1.2	Yes	The at-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fixed moment in time is the share of young people under 18 whose equivalised disposable income in a survey year is below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold from the base year 2005 in relation to the total population of the same age group. The 2005 threshold is recalculated to the survey year by means of the consumer price index. This indicator keeps the poverty threshold fixed in real terms over a longer period of time and therefore controls the effects of a moving poverty threshold. To allow for these sudden fluctuations in poverty thresholds and avoid misleading results in periods of rapid and general economic deterioration, Eurostat calculates the at-risk-of-poverty indicator anchored in time.	Sex	EU-SILC	2006-2013	31, from 2010: 29
<i>b. Depth of poverty</i>							
Relative at-risk-of-poverty gap by poverty threshold	1.1.3	Yes	The Relative at-risk-of-poverty gap displays the difference between the median equivalised income of persons aged 0-17 below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold at 60% of median equivalised income and the threshold itself, expressed as a percentage of the at-risk-of-poverty threshold (%).	Sex	EU-SILC	2004-2014	31, from 2010: 29
<i>c. Persistence of poverty</i>							
Persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate	1.1.4	Yes	The persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate shows the percentage of the young people (18-24) living in households where the equivalised disposable income was below the at-risk-of-poverty threshold for the current year and at least two out of the preceding three years in relation to the total population of the same age group. The at-risk-of-poverty threshold is calculated as 60% of median equivalised income. Its calculation requires a longitudinal instrument, through which the individuals are followed over four years.	Sex	EU-SILC	2007-2013	From 2008: 30; from 2010: 29

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
1.2. Material deprivation							
Severe material deprivation	1.2.1	Yes	Severe material deprivation rate is defined as the share of young people (15-29) who are enforced unable to pay for at least four of the following-mentioned items in relation to the total population of the same age group: (a) to pay their rent, mortgage or utility bills; (b) to keep their home adequately warm; (c) to face unexpected expenses; (d) to eat meat or proteins regularly; (e) to go on holiday; (f) a television set; (g) a washing machine; (h) a car; (i) a telephone. Material deprivation refers to a state of economic strain and durables, defined as the enforced inability (rather than the choice not to do so) to pay unexpected expenses, afford a one-week annual holiday away from home, a meal involving meat, chicken or fish every second day, the adequate heating of a dwelling, durable goods like a washing machine, colour television, telephone or car, being confronted with payment arrears (mortgage or rent, utility bills, hire purchase instalments or other loan payments). The material deprivation rate is an indicator in EU-SILC that expresses the inability to afford some items considered by most people to be desirable or even necessary to lead an adequate life. The indicator distinguishes between individuals who cannot afford a certain good or service, and those who do not have this good or service for another reason, e.g. because they do not want or do not need it.	Sex, age groups a), country of birth, household status	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2005:30; from 2010: 29
Unmet needs for medical examination	1.2.2	Yes	The share of young people (16-29) who declare self-reported unmet needs for medical examination because it is too expensive or too far to travel or there is a waiting list in relation to the total population of the same age group. Person's own assessment of whether he or she needed examination or treatment for a specific type of health care, but didn't have it or didn't seek for it. EU-SILC collects data on two types of health care services: medical care and dental care.	Sex, age groups b), income quintiles	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2005: 30; from 2010: 29
Inability of making ends meet	1.2.3	No	The inability of making ends meet refers to the proportion of young people living in a household with the ability of making ends meet with difficulty or great difficulty (EM D/GD) in relation to the total population of the same age group.	Sex, age group a; household type, highest education of parents, poverty status	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2005: 30; from 2010: 29
1.3 Housing							
<i>a. Overcrowding</i>							
Overcrowding rate	1.3.1	Yes	The overcrowding rate is defined as the share of young people (15-29) living in an overcrowded household in relation to the total population of the same age group. A person is considered as living in an overcrowded household if the household does not have at its disposal a minimum number of rooms equal to: one room for the household; one room per couple in the household; one room for each single person aged 18 or more; one room per pair of single people of the same gender between 12 and 17 years of age; one room for each single person between 12 and 17 years of age and not included in the previous category; one room per pair of children under 12 years of age.	Sex, age groups a), poverty status	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2005: 30; from 2010: 29

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
<i>b. Housing costs</i>							
Housing cost overburden rate	1.3.2	Yes	The housing cost overburden rate is the share of young people (15-29) living in households where the total housing costs ('net' of housing allowances) represent more than 40 % of disposable income ('net' of housing allowances) in relation to the total population of the same age group.	Sex, age groups a), poverty status	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2005: 30; from 2010: 29
Home ownership rate	1.3.3	No	Share of young people (18-29) who declare that the household is living in a dwelling owned by their own (or by a household member) in relation to the total population of young people (18-29) who already left home. This indicator is based on the household level, meaning that the household respondent gives the information about the household's tenure status. The owner of the accommodation should be a member of the household. The household respondent is the person from whom household level information is obtained. Given that the household-level response is going to be attributed to all household members, it is essential that the information be collected from someone who can, in some sense, 'speak for' the household. The household respondent will be chosen according to the following priorities: Priority (1): the person responsible for the accommodation. Priority (2): a household member aged 16 and over who is the best placed to give the information.	Sex	EU-SILC	2005-2010	30
<i>c. Housing deprivation</i>							
Severe housing deprivation	1.3.4	Yes	Severe housing deprivation rate is defined as the share of young people (15-29) living in the dwelling which is considered as overcrowded, while also exhibiting at least one of the housing deprivation measures, in relation to the total population of the same age group. Housing deprivation is a measure of poor amenities and is calculated by referring to those households with a leaking roof, no bath/shower and no indoor toilet, or a dwelling considered too dark.	Sex, age groups a), poverty status	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2005: 30; from 2010: 29
1.4 Poverty and social exclusion (EU2020)							
At risk of poverty or social exclusion	1.4.1	Yes	The at risk of poverty or social exclusion rate refers to the situation of young people (15-29) people either: (1) at risk of poverty, or (2) severely materially deprived; or (3) living in a household with a very low work intensity. The indicator displays the share of young people (15-29) who are at risk of poverty or social exclusion in relation to the total population of the same age group.	Sex, age groups a), country of birth, household status	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2005: 30; from 2010: 29

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
2. Labour market attachment and work balance							
2.1 Labour market attachment							
<i>a. Employment</i>							
Youth employment rate	2.1.1	No	The employment rate is the share of employed young persons (15-29) in relation to the total population of the same age group. For the overall employment rate, the comparison is made with the population of working-age; but employment rates can also be calculated for a particular age group and/or gender in a specific geographical area (for example the males of age 15-24 employed versus total in one European Union (EU) Member State). Employment/activity rates represent employed/active persons as a percentage of same age total population.	Sex, age groups a), educational attainment level a), country of birth	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29
<i>b. Precarious employment</i>							
Temporary employment rate	2.1.2	No	The share of young people (15-29) who declare to be temporarily employed in relation to the total number of employees of the same age group. Temporary employment includes work under a fixed-term contract, as against permanent work where there is no end-date. A job may be considered temporary employment (and its holder a temporary employee) if both employer and employee agree that its end is decided by objective rules (usually written down in a work contract of limited life). These rules can be a specific date, the end of a task, or the return of another employee who has been temporarily replaced.	Sex, age groups a), country of birth	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29
Involuntary part-time employment	2.1.3	No	Part-time employment rates represent young people (15-29) employed on a part-time basis as a share of the total part-time population of same age group. Persons working on an involuntary part-time basis are those who declare that they work part-time because they are unable to find full-time work. Full-time/part-time distinction in the main job is made on the basis of a spontaneous answer given by the respondent in all countries, except for the Netherlands, Iceland and Norway, where part-time is determined on the basis of whether the usual hours worked are fewer than 35, while full-time on the basis of whether the usual hours worked are 35 or more, and in Sweden where this criterion is applied to the self-employed persons as well.	Sex, age groups a)	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
<i>c. Self-employment</i> Youth self-employment	2.1.4	No	Percentage of self-employed among all employed aged 15-29. A self-employed person is the sole or joint owner of the unincorporated enterprise (one that has not been incorporated i.e. formed into a legal corporation) in which he/she works, unless they are also in paid employment which is their main activity (in that case, they are considered to be employees). Self-employed people also include: unpaid family workers; outworkers (who work outside the usual workplace, such as at home); workers engaged in production done entirely for their own final use or own capital formation, either individually or collectively. Self-employed persons are the ones who work in their own business, farm or professional practice. A self-employed person is considered to be working if she/he meets one of the following criteria: works for the purpose of earning profit, spends time on the operation of a business or is in the process of setting up his/her business.	Sex, age groups a), educational attainment level a)	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29
<i>d. Unemployment</i> Youth unemployment rate	2.1.5	No	The youth unemployment rate is the share of young people (15-29) who are unemployed in relation to the labour force (employed and unemployed) of the total population of the same age group. An unemployed person is defined by Eurostat, according to the guidelines of the International Labour Organization, as: - without work during the reference week; - available to start work within the next two weeks (or has already found a job to start within the next three months); - actively having sought employment at some time during the last four weeks.	Sex, age groups a), educational attainment level a), country of birth	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29
Youth long-term unemployment rate (12 months or longer)	2.1.6	No	Youth Long-term unemployment refers to the share of young people (15-29) who are out of work and have been actively seeking unemployment for at least a year in relation to the total population of the same age group. An unemployed young person is defined as being aged 15 to 29 who was without work during the reference week, was currently available for work and was either actively seeking work in the last four weeks or had already found a job to start within the next three months. The unemployment period is defined as the duration of a job search, or as the length of time since the last job was held (if shorter than the time spent on a job search). This definition follows International Labour Organisation guidelines.	Sex, age groups a)	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
Not in employment and not in any education and training rate (NEET)	2.1.7	No	<p>The indicator young people neither in employment nor in education and training (NEET) corresponds to the share of people of a given age group (15-29) who is not employed and not involved in further education or training in relation to the total population of the same age group. The numerator of the indicator refers to persons meeting these two conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - they are not employed (i.e. unemployed or inactive according to the International Labour Organisation definition); - they have not received any education or training in the four weeks preceding the survey. The denominator is the total population of the same age group and sex, excluding the respondents who have not answered the question 'participation to regular education and training'. <p>When broken down by educational attainment level, the numerator consists in people 'NEET' at a given education level while the denominator consists in people 'NEET' at any education level, i.e. the data is presented in percentage points of the overall NEET rates for a given age and sex. Due to no answers to the variable 'participation in education and training' or 'educational attainment level', certain breakdowns of NEET rates may not exactly sum up to the overall NEET rate for a given age group and sex.</p>	Sex, age groups a), activity status, educational attainment level b)	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29
<p><i>e. Labour market attachment of households</i></p> <p>Households with very low work intensity</p>	2.1.8	Yes	<p>The indicator persons living in households with low work intensity is defined as the share of young people (15-29) living in a household having a work intensity below a threshold set at 0.20 in relation to all the total population of the same age group. The work intensity of a household is the ratio of the total number of months that all working-age household members have worked during the income reference year and the total number of months the same household members theoretically could have worked in the same period. A working-age person is a person aged 18-59 years, with the exclusion of students in the age group between 18 and 24 years. Households composed only of children, of students aged less than 25 and/or people aged 60 or more are completely excluded from the indicator calculation.</p>	Sex, age groups a), country of birth, household status	EU-LFS	2004-2012	From 2005: 30; from 2010: 29
<p>2.2 Work-life balance</p> <p><i>a. Work and leisure</i></p> <p>Employees usually working long hours</p>	2.2.1	No	<p>The share of employees (15-29) working 40 hours or more per week in relation to all employees of the same age group. This indicator contains data on employment by hour bands for usual weekly hours worked in the main job. Actual hours of work instead of usual hours of work are only available in some countries (Japan and Korea).</p>	Sex, age groups a), employment status	OECD Collection: diverse sample surveys	2004-2012	29

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
<i>b. Work and care</i>							
Working part-time or reduced hours because of caring responsibilities	2.2.2	No	Working part-time or reduced hours because of caring responsibilities represent young persons (15-29) employed on a part-time basis due to looking after children or incapacitated adults as a share of all part-time employees of the same age group. Full-time/part-time distinction in the main job is made on the basis of a spontaneous answer given by the respondent in all countries, except for the Netherlands, Iceland and Norway, where part-time is determined on the basis of whether the usual hours worked are fewer than 35, while full-time on the basis of whether the usual hours worked are 35 or more, and in Sweden where this criterion is applied to the self-employed persons as well.	Sex, age groups a)	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29
Inactive because of caring responsibilities	2.2.3	No	The share of young people (15-29) who are inactive due to caring for children or incapacitated adults in relation to all inactive people of the same age group. A person is economically inactive, according to the International Labour Organisation definition, if he or she is not part of the labour force. So inactive people are neither employed nor unemployed. The inactive population can include pre-school children, school children, students, pensioners and housewives or -men, for example, provided that they are not working at all and not available or looking for work either; some of these may be of working-age.	Sex, age groups a)	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29
3. Education and training							
3.1 Access to and quality of education							
<i>a. Educational attainment</i>							
Highest education attainment levels (5-8)	3.1.1	No	Youth education attainment level is defined as the share of young people (15-29) who have successfully completed ISCED education level of 5-8 in relation to all the total population of the same age group who successfully completed any ISCED education level. The expression 'level successfully completed' must be associated with obtaining a certificate or a diploma, when there is a certification. In cases where there is no certification, successful completion must be associated with full attendance. When determining the highest level, both general and vocational education/training should be taken into consideration. Data on educational attainment exclude persons who did not answer to the question 'highest level of education or training successfully completed'. This statistical indicator is calculated by dividing the number of young people who meet this attainment level (numerator) by the total population of the 20-24 age group (denominator); without however counting in this total population those who gave 'no answer' to the Labour force survey question on the 'highest level of education or training attained'.	Sex, age groups a)	EU-LFS	2004-2014	29

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
Enrolments of the youth population in tertiary educational tracks	3.1.2	No	The share of students (15-29) enrolled in tertiary education (ISCED 5-6) refers to the count of students studying in the reference period (2004-2012) in any tertiary education programme full-time or part-time in relation to the all enrolled students at the age of 15-29. Each student enrolled in the education programmes covered by the corresponding category is counted once and only once. National data collection systems permitting, the statistics reflect the number of students enrolled at the beginning of the school/academic year. Preferably, the end (or near-end) of the first month of the school/academic year is chosen (special arrangements are made for part-year students who may not start studies at the beginning of the school year). At the tertiary level the enrolment of students may not be stable enough at the beginning of the academic year and therefore a count at a later point may be preferable. Adult education programmes cover the learning activity of those returning to education after having left initial (or 'regular') education. Only programmes (of at least one semester) that are similar to regular education (in subject content or potential qualifications) are included. In some countries, there are, in addition, adult educations that are not similar to regular education; these programmes are not included.	Age groups a)	UNESCO-OECD-Eurostat (UOE) data collection on education statistics	2004-2012	30
<i>b. Lifelong learning</i> Non-formal education and training	3.1.3	No	The share of young people (15-29) who participated in non-formal education or training within the last four weeks before the interview in relation to the total population of the same age group. Non-formal education and training is defined as any organised and sustained learning activities that do not correspond exactly to the above definition of formal education. Non-formal education may therefore take place both within and outside educational institutions and cater to people of all ages. Depending on national contexts, it may cover educational programmes to impart adult literacy, life-skills, work-skills, and general culture.	Sex, age groups a)	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29
3.2 Educational achievement <i>a. Achievement in basic skills</i> Two or more foreign languages	3.2.1	No	The share of young people learning two or more foreign languages in relation to the total population of enrolled young people.	Education	Eurostat data collection on language learning in schools, UOE	2005-2012	29

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
<i>b. Early school leaving</i> No longer in education or training	3.2.2	No	Early leaver from education and training, previously named early school leaver, generally refers to a person aged 18 to 24 who has finished no more than a lower secondary education and is not involved in further education or training. The denominator in the total population consists of the same age group, excluding the respondents who have not answered the questions 'highest level of education or training successfully completed' and 'participation to education and training'. For Eurostat statistical purposes, an early leaver from education and training is operationally defined as a person aged 18 to 24 recorded in the Labour force survey (LFS): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - whose highest level of education or training attained is ISCED 0, 1, 2 or 3c short; - who received no education or training in the four weeks preceding the survey. The 'early leavers from education and training' statistical indicator is then calculated by dividing the number of early leavers from education and training, as defined above, by the total population of the same age group in the Labour force survey.	Sex, labour status	EU-LFS	2004-2013	29
4. Health and risk behaviours							
4.1 Health status							
<i>a. Objective health status</i> Long-standing illness or health problem	4.1.1	Yes	The share of young people (16-29) who declare to suffer from any longstanding (of a duration of at least six months) illness or health problem in relation to the total population of the same age.	Sex, age groups b), income quintiles	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2005: 30; from 2010: 29
<i>b. Subjective health status</i> Self-perceived health	4.1.2	Yes	The share of young people (16-29) who perceives his/her health in general as bad or very bad in relation to all young people (16-29) answering to this question. The concept is operationalised by a question on how a person perceives his/her health in general using one of the answer categories very good/ good/ fair/ bad/ very bad. Indicators based on this concept can be used to evaluate the general health status, health inequalities and health care needs at the population level.	Sex, age groups b), income quintiles	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2004: 30; from 2010: 29
4.2. Health behaviour							
<i>a. Physical activity</i> Practice of daily physical activity	4.2.1	Yes	Percentage of the youth population (15-34) practising at least 30 minutes of physical activity (moderate or intense) per day.	Sex, age groups d), educational attainment level a)	EHIS	2008	31
<i>b. Obesity</i> Obesity of young people	4.2.2	Yes	The share of young people (15-29) who have a BMI greater than 30 in relation to the total population of young people (15-29).	Sex, age groups a), income quintiles	EHIS	2008	31

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
4.3. Risk behaviour							
<i>a. Smoking</i>							
Young daily smokers	4.3.1	No	The share of young (15-29) people who smoke cigarettes daily in relation to the total population of young people (15-29).	Sex, age groups a), income quintiles	EHIS	2008	31
<i>b. Alcohol consumption</i>							
Hazardous alcohol consumption	4.3.2	No	The share of young people (15-34) who declare to have hazardous patterns of alcohol consumption (binge drinking) daily or almost daily in relation to the total population of 15-34 year olds who declare to have an alcoholic drink more often than once a month. The following categories are used for the dissemination: never drink or drink occasionally/drink regularly but don't binge drink/drink regularly and binge drink but less than once a month/binge drink monthly/binge drink weekly/binge drink daily or almost daily).	Sex, age groups a), educational attainment level a), income quintiles	EHIS	2008	29
<i>c. Illicit drugs</i>							
Illicit drug use	4.3.3	No	Percentage of young people (15-34) who report having used any medicine, resp. medicine for pain non-prescribed by a physician during the past 2 weeks..	Sex, age groups d), educational attainment level a)	EHIS	2008	29
<i>d. Teenage pregnancy</i>							
Adolescent fertility rate	4.3.4	No	Adolescent fertility rate is the number of births per 1,000 women ages 15-19. Adolescent fertility rates are based on data on registered live births from vital registration systems or, in the absence of such systems, from censuses or sample surveys. The estimated rates are generally considered reliable measures of fertility in the recent past. Where no empirical information on age-specific fertility rates is available, a model is used to estimate the share of births to adolescents. For countries without vital registration systems fertility rates are generally based on extrapolations from trends observed in censuses or surveys from earlier years. Reproductive health is a state of physical and mental well-being in relation to the reproductive system and its functions and processes. Means of achieving reproductive health include education and services during pregnancy and childbirth, safe and effective contraception, and prevention and treatment of sexually transmitted diseases. Complications of pregnancy and childbirth are the leading cause of death and disability among women of reproductive age in developing countries.		World Development Indicators	2004-2012	29
<i>e. Psychological distress</i>							
Psychological distress	4.3.5	No	Psychological distress is based on the Mental Health Inventory (MHI-5) which consists of three depression-related items and two anxiety-related items. It has a score of 0 to 100, where a score of 100 represents optimal mental health. The indicator is presented in the form of average score. For instance in Bulgaria the average score of population aged 15-24 is equal to 85.4 whereas in 73.3 in Malta.	Sex	EHIS	2008	2 3 9 13 14 17 18 20 21 23 24 25

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
<i>f. Suicide</i> Crude death rate by suicide	4.3.6	No	The share of young people (15-29) who commit suicide what is derived from death certificates. The crude death rate by suicide describes mortality in relation to the total population. Expressed in deaths per 100,000 inhabitants, it is calculated as the number of deaths recorded in the population for a given period divided by population in the same period and then multiplied by 100,000. The Crude death rate by suicide of young people is calculated for 5-year age groups. At this level of detail, comparisons between countries and regions are meaningful. The crude death rate for the total population (all ages) however, is a weighted average of the age-specific mortality rates. The weighting factor is the age distribution of the population whose mortality is being observed. Thus, the population structure strongly influences this indicator for broad age classes. In a relatively 'old' population, there will be more deaths than in a 'young' one because mortality is higher for age groups referring to older ages.	Sex, age groups a)	Causes of Death	2004-2010	29
5. Social connections and participation							
5.1 Family and peer relationships							
<i>a. Family relationships</i> Living together with parents	5.1.1	No	The share of young people (16-29) living in one household with their parents in relation to the total population of young people (16-29). A 'private household' means 'a person living alone or a group of people who live together in the same private dwelling and share expenditures, including the joint provision of the essentials of living'. EU-SILC implementing regulation number 1983/2003 on updated definitions, defines households in terms of sharing household expenses and (for non-permanent members) in terms of duration of stay and (for temporarily absent members) in terms of duration of absence.	Sex, age groups b)	EU-SILC	2004-2012	From 2005:30; from 2010: 29
Contact with relatives	5.1.2	Yes	The share of young people (16-29) who get together or have contact never or at least once a year with their relatives in relation to the total population of young people (16-29).	Sex, age groups b)	EU-SILC	2006	30
Single adult with children in household	5.1.3	No	Share of young people (15-24) in living in the following type of household: Single adult with children in relation to adults with children same age group.		EU-LFS	2005-2014	29
5.2 Civic participation							
<i>a. Voting/ Voting turnout</i> Youth non-voting rate	5.2.1	No	The share of young people (18-29) declaring that they did not vote at the last election in relation to the total population of that age group.	Sex	ESS	2004-2012	From 2004: 30 from 2008: 29

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Domain/component/subcomponent	Code (Y+)	Over-arching?	Definition	Breakdowns	Data source	Time coverage	Country coverage
<i>b. Volunteering</i> Occasionally unpaid voluntary work	5.2.2	Yes	Share of young people (15-29) reporting at least occasionally unpaid voluntary work through the following organisations: - Community and social services (e.g. organisations helping the elderly, young people, disabled or other people in need). - Educational, cultural, sports or professional associations - Social movements (for example environmental, human rights) or charities (for example fundraising, campaigning) - Political parties, trade unions - Other voluntary organisations	Sex, age group a)	EQLS	2007-2012	29
<i>c. Group membership</i> Trade union membership: past 12 months	5.2.3	No	The share of young people (15-29) who have been member of a trade union or similar organisation in the past 12 month in relation to the total population of young people (15-29).	Sex	ESS	2004-2012	From 2004: 30 from 2008: 29
<i>d. Internet use</i> Personal use of www	5.2.4	No	The share of young people (15-29) declaring that they use the internet, the World Wide Web or e-mail - whether at home or at work - for their personal use at least once a month in relation to the total population of this age group.	Sex	ESS	2004-2010	From 2004: 30 from 2008: 29
6. Environmental quality and physical safety							
6.1 Environmental quality							
<i>a. Outside air pollution</i> Pollution, grime or other environmental problems	6.1.1	Yes	The share of young people (15-29) living in households with reported pollution, grime or other environmental problems.	Poverty status	EU-SILC	2005-2012	From 2005: 30; from 2010: 29
<i>b. Noise</i> Noise from neighbours or from the street	6.1.2	Yes	The share of young people (15-29) living in households with reporting noise from neighbours or from street	Poverty status	EU-SILC	2005-2010	From 2005: 30 from 2010: 29
6.2 Physical safety							
Road traffic injuries: 12 month	6.2.1	No	The share of young people aged 15-24 reporting to have had a road traffic accident, which resulted in injury for which medical treatment was sought during the last 12 month in relation to the total population of that age group.	Sex	EHIS	2008	BE BG CZ EL ES CY LV HU MT PL RO SL SK TUR
Crime, violence or vandalism in the area	6.2.2	Yes	The share of young people (15-29) living in households with reported crime, violence or vandalism in the area	poverty status	EU-SILC	2005-2010	29

Table 5.3 Proposed Indicators for IPOLIS Youth Module: Indicator Fiche (continued)

Note:	
1: country coverage does not specify the number of countries included but is an internal code for number of countries included.	
Breakdowns have been disaggregated as follows (see Chapter 5):	
Sex:	a. male, b. female.
Age groups:	a) 15-19; 20-24; 25-29;
	b) 16-19; 20-24; 25-29;
	c) 16-24; 18-24;
	d) 15-24; 25-34.
Household status:	a. person living with parents, b. person not living with parents.
Income quintiles:	a. first quintile, b. second quintile, c. third quintile, d. fourth quintile, e. fifth quintile.
Educational attainment level:	a) a. ISCED 0-2, b. ISCED 3-4, c. ISCED 5-6;
	b) a. ISCED 0-2, b. ISCED 3-6.
Labour status:	a. employed, b. not employed.
Education:	a. general (ISCED 3) b. vocational and pre-vocational.
Employment status:	a. dependent, b. self-employed, c. total.
Country of birth:	a. foreign country, b. reporting country.
Activity status:	a. unemployed, b. inactive.
Poverty status:	a. below 60% of the median equivalised income, b. above 60% of the median equivalised income.

Source Own illustration; information about and definitions of indicators are mainly taken from the metadata banks where the indicators have been published or from the Eurostat Glossary when adequate or own definitions have been created

6. Measuring quality of life and well-being for youth: specific problems

The following section describes specific problems of the IPOLIS youth module concerning:

- a) availability of indicators within domains, and
- b) missing and underreporting of values within indicators.

Generally, there exist very few datasets covering youth-specific topics for the defined age group of 15-29 year olds. However, the most household-based comparative datasets like EU-SILC, EU-LFS, or ESS include this age group and allow specific indicators to be broken down for youth and age bands. The domain-specific data gaps and problems will also be discussed.

Within the domain '*Material living conditions*', several indicators across all components contain many missing values (often 50% or more) for the year 2004 due to missing country data. In these cases, the continuous country coverage starts in the survey year 2005 only. Furthermore, Turkey, Switzerland, and Croatia are underreported (often only 1-3 years) in this domain. One specific problem in building the IPOLIS database for youth indicators was including an indicator on non-material wealth. Consequently, we decided to measure wealth by observing the tenure status of this age group, whereby homeownership is considered as an indicator for wealth. At this point, one has to consider that the indicator 'Home ownership rate' is based on the household level. Therefore, we do not know which member of the household is the outright owner of the dwelling since the ownership is assigned to all household members. Hence, it is problematic to disaggregate the indicator by sex because we do not know if only one household member is the outright owner or (if applicable) multiple members of the household possess the dwelling. Due to this fact, the breakdown by sex is only useful to achieve an overview of the share of men and women living in owner-occupied households. Besides this, the data for the indicator were only available for the survey years 2005-2010. In the year 2010, only a small proportion of the country sample is provided.¹⁶ Due to longer educational phases, and therefore a later start of employment, it would make sense to exclude the early adolescents from this indicator. Hence, this indicator is available for adolescents between ages 18-29 years. The 'At-risk-of-poverty rate anchored at a fixed moment in time' is only available for adolescents younger than 18 years. The 'Persistent at-risk-of-poverty rate' contains many missing values (50%) in the survey year 2007.

In 2004 and 2005, several indicators of the domain '*Labour market attachment and work-life balance*' show missing values for Turkey and the Former Yugoslav Republic. For these countries, further missing values exist for several other survey years. The indicator 'Employees usually working long hours' was available in absolute numbers only. We calculated the relative numbers on our own by summing up all response categories (1-19 hours, 20-29 hours, 30-34 hours, 35-39 hours, 40 hours or more) for each country and using this total sum as a denominator. A more country-specific problem occurred for the measurement of 'Working part-time or reduced hours because of caring responsibilities'. The distinction between full-time and part-time employment is made on the basis of a spontaneous answer given by the respondents in all countries, except for the Netherlands, Ice-

¹⁶ Values based on a too small sample were excluded (e.g. Norway 2010).

land, and Norway. Working part-time or reduced hours because of caring responsibilities is determined on the basis of whether the usual hours worked per week are fewer than 35 (part-time employment), while the full-time equivalent is determined by usual hours worked per week being greater than 35. This criterion is applied to the self-employed persons in Sweden as well. In sum, there is no adjustment to the country-specific regulations of weekly working hours, even if some countries, or even parts of some countries, apply 40 hours of work per week. The same holds for the measurement of 'Involuntary part-time' employment, since this indicator is based upon the measurement of part-time employment. Additionally, there are many missing values for the youth population occurring in the indicator 'Working part-time or reduced hours because of caring responsibilities' and 'Inactive because of caring responsibilities'. Both working part-time or reduced hours and inactivity are due to caring obligations, which explain the rather small shares of missing values regarding the youth population. Considering that many people in this age span are childless, these missing values consist of values with a very low reliability or provisional values. For men, this concern is even stronger.

Nearly all indicators of the domain '*Education and training*' include several indicator values for some countries and survey years with a low reliability or even provisional values. Furthermore, there are several breaks in the time series leading to low comparability over time. The indicator 'Enrolments of the youth population in tertiary educational tracks' was provided in absolute numbers only. Again, we calculated the relative numbers on our own by computing the share of tertiary-enrolled students of the total population using the same age groups in each country. The indicator 'Two or more foreign languages' exists only from 2005 onwards. Moreover, the values for Germany are completely missing for this indicator.

The domain '*Health and risk behaviours*' has severe data gaps. Besides the fact that the indicators of health status have many missing values in the year 2004, some values are of low reliability or are estimated values. Contrary to the indicator selection criteria for the IOPLIS database, the objective health status is provided as a subjective measure of objective circumstances. Furthermore, the subjective health status is supplied as a self-perception of health status. Again, there are several missing values, namely for Croatia, Turkey, and Switzerland. Many indicators of the health behaviours and risk behaviour category are only collected and offered for one year (usually 2008) and for a smaller selection of EU countries (12-17 countries). This holds true for instance for the indicator 'Practice of daily physical activity'.

The domain '*Social connectedness and civic participation*' includes several indicators which we calculated directly. The shares of the indicators 'Single adult with children in household', 'Youth non-voting rate', 'Occasionally unpaid voluntary work', 'Trade union membership: past 12 months', and 'Personal use of www' were calculated using the absolute numbers of each indicator and the total numbers of the population of the explicit age or/and status group. Moreover, the estimates for the indicators 'Youth non-voting rate', 'Trade union membership: past 12 months', and 'Personal use of www' were only collected every two years from 2004 onwards. In fact, there was another indicator within the ICT dataset which was recently published referring to the frequency of internet use among the youth population. Nevertheless, this indicator is provided for the survey years 2011-2013 only. For this reason, we decided to stick to our direct calculations of the ESS-based indicator, which covers an essentially larger portion of the time span. In addition, the indicator 'Contact with relatives' exists only for 2006 and displays estimates with a low reliability for Ireland, the Netherlands, and Norway.

7. Recommendations for the improvement of measurement and data infrastructure: the way forward

In line with the recommendations stated by Gábos and Kopasz (2015) in their report on the child module for IPOLIS, we focus on three aspects of recommendations to the European Commission: (a) the lack of, and need for, the extension of indicators within domains and components; (b) the extension of the survey population to hard-to-reach young people; and (c) the consideration of longitudinal data. In addition to these three points, we start by discussing more general difficulties or challenges of monitoring youth that relate to the transitions from youth to adulthood.

7.1 Challenges of monitoring youth (in) transitions

Youth is a phase in life that is characterised by transitions into adulthood. The ‘big five’ transitions that are considered as most important are:

- a) leaving the parental home and forming an independent household;
- b) obtaining education and qualifications;
- c) entering the labour market;
- d) forming partnership and marriage, and
- e) becoming a parent.

Each of these transitions bears its own risks and can fail. Monitoring the extent to which these transitions are successfully mastered can thus be considered relevant information for monitoring youth. Although youth indicator systems do provide information that directly or indirectly relate to these transitions, thus far they do not address these transitions as such.

Moreover, the fact that this period is one of transitioning from economic dependency to independence complicates matters when aiming to monitor youth well-being based on survey data. This is particularly the case for leaving the parental home and forming an independent household, which is not only an important transition in its own right, but has consequences for all indicators that refer to the household level. This is the case for almost all indicators in the domain of ‘*Material living conditions*’ (see for example, the discussion for the indicator of home ownership above). Some youth might still live with their parents, while others already live independently. In the first case, household-related indicators such as poverty and material well-being reflect the conditions of the parental household and thus, the socialisation of the youth. In the second case, the indicator reflects the living condition of the young person as an independent young adult. However, these two situations can give a very different picture for the same person right before and after leaving the parental home. A young person from a very affluent family might leave the parental home for university studies. When surveyed right before leaving, this young person appears to live in a wealthy household with high incomes, wealth, and material living conditions. When surveyed right after leaving the parental home, the same young person might be found on rather low incomes and in a small apartment with no wealth (i.e. in poverty and material deprivation). This is likely to be the case in many European countries, where the time of higher education studies is still considered as a period of ‘deferred gratification’. Above and beyond this tradition, the stage of attaining higher education

or vocational training is oftentimes economically precarious. As human capital theory states, human capital accumulation is an investment that comes at the expense of current consumption for the sake of future consumption. As such, the material living conditions during this period can lead to false conclusions about youth well-being and future life chances. In other words, taking the data and indicators as they are, it is likely that we overestimate the extent of poverty and material deprivation of young adults in Europe. At the same time, we probably underestimate the extent to which youth poverty is actually related to parental background, and thus, impacts on future life chances (for the case of Germany, see Groh-Samberg & Voges, 2014).

There is no simple solution to this. However, one possibility that we highly recommend is to provide - whenever possible - breakdowns for all indicators by 'living with at least one parent' and 'living independently'. So far, however, this breakdown is not considered for indicator systems on youth. In many datasets, this information is either missing or complicated to compute. Moving even beyond this, we recommend including (proxy) information on parental background in European surveys for young people living independently. If this information would be available, breakdowns of indicators of youth well-being by parental background would become possible. Finally, information on intergenerational support (in both directions, from parents to children as well as from children to parents) is highly relevant in this regard.

7.2 Extension of youth monitoring in terms of lack of indicators and further disaggregation of indicators

The potential pool of policy-relevant, timely, cross-country comparable, and robust indicators is large and the underlying data infrastructure is rich in regard to most of the quality of life domains (e.g. *'Material living conditions'*, *'Labour market attachment and work-life balance'*, and *'Education and training'*). In the case of the domains and components regarding *'Health and risk behaviours'*, *'Social connectedness and civic participation'*, as well as *'Environmental quality and physical safety'*, the indicator coverage and the data infrastructure are poorer. For all domains, however, gaps can be identified and thus the monitoring of the youth can be improved. We list the most relevant gaps by domain and provide some recommendations for improving the monitoring of youth where possible. Additionally, we discuss the relevance of additional disaggregation of indicators.

a. Domain 'Material living conditions'

As mentioned above, little information and ready-to-use indicators can be found on the formation of independent households among youth. This includes indicators concerning sharing of income and expenditure among households and between households, which would serve to view the extent of (in)dependence of households and members of households. This also leads back to the question of whether poverty thresholds based on household income and expenditure are sufficient for conveying intra-household inequalities, even though disaggregated by sex. A threshold based on individual income or consumption could be considered. However, there is a lack of consensus on the definition of consumption and a lack of surveys which collect household or individual-level consumption information. Moreover, information on the extent to which household expenditures are shared among households and household members is also limited. In line with the 2010 EU-SILC module such information could be measures at least ones.

b. Domain 'Labour market attachment and work life balance'

An indicator on the employability of youth, or the extent to which skills that youth bring to the labour market are those that are demanded by employers, would shed light on the question of the link between supply and demand. However, the measurement criteria for the employability of youth are difficult to determine.

As reconciling work and family life has become a major public policy concern in many countries, indicators on (shares of) responsibility for family care (i.e., child and elder care) and household work, as well as flexible hours, could improve the policy assessment of work-family issues. These would extend beyond caring for children since other family members may also require care, in relation to material living conditions.

c. Domain 'Education and training'

Existing data lacks information on components such as early childhood education.

d. Domain 'Health and risk behaviours'

Existing data lacks information on components such as bullying and fighting.

e. Domain 'Social connectedness and civic participation'

Existing data lacks more detailed information on components such as peer relationships for youth.

f. Further disaggregation of indicators

One main issue to improve upon would be the extent to which existing data on youth can be disaggregated to subnational levels, or by urban and rural residence. Of particular interest would be, for instance, the rate of growth in youth employment or indicators on environmental quality, such as pollution, noise, or crime among youth in urban and rural areas. However, possibilities for disaggregating existing data to sub-national levels are limited.

7.3 Extending youth monitoring to hard-to-reach young people

The sampling frame includes private households only and is usually taken from population registers, of which currency and reliability may greatly vary across countries. This procedure excludes hard-to-reach youth populations. Hard-to-reach groups like migrants, refugees, displaced young persons, street youth, indigenous and minority youth, rural youth, and young people with disabilities are under- or unrepresented in most survey samples, even though they are often strongly affected by poverty or social exclusion.

7.4 Considering longitudinal data collection

Former work on youth has stressed the importance of panel data. Longitudinal surveys or individual-level anonymised administrative data could add remarkable value. Repeated information on individuals can contribute to the indicator development process by establishing relationships between resources or inputs in early life stages and outcomes in later life stages. The longitudinal database of the EU-SILC, for instance, could be used to measure such indicators.

appendix 1 Timeline on EU/CoE decisions/ resolutions/conclusions/regulations on Youth (2000-2013)

In this section we provide an overview on regulations, decisions, and conclusions on EU youth policy from 2000 to 2013. The year and name of the intervention, as well as the link to the document and the date of document are given.

2000

European Parliament legislative resolution on the joint text approved by the Conciliation Committee for a European Parliament and Council decision establishing the Community action programme for youth (C5-0116/2000 - 1998/0197(COD))

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52000AP0100&rid=6>

Date of document: 13/04/2000

Decision No 1031/2000/EC Of The European Parliament And Of The Council of 13 April 2000 establishing the 'Youth' Community action programme (OJ L 117, 18.5.2000, p. 1)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02000D1031-20040430&rid=3>

Date of document: 30/04/2004

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02000D1031-20040501&rid=2>

Date of document: 01/05/2004

2001

European Commission white paper - A new impetus for European youth /*COM/2001/0681 final */

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52001DC0681&rid=2>

Date of document: 21/11/2001

2002

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, of 14 February 2002 on the added value of voluntary activity for young people in the context of the development of Community action on youth

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42002X0223%2801%29&rid=7>

Date of document: 14/02/2002

Council Conclusions on the follow-up of the Commission White Paper entitled 'A new impetus for European youth'

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52002XG0522%2801%29&rid=6>

Date of document: 22/05/2002

Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council of 27 June 2002 regarding the framework of European cooperation in the youth field

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32002G0713%2801%29&rid=5>

Date of document: 27/06/2002

Council Conclusions of 14 October 2002 on Special Report No 2/2002 by the Court of Auditors on the Socrates and Youth for Europe Community action programmes

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52002XG1022%2801%29&rid=4>

Date of document: 14/10/2002

European Parliament resolution on the implementation of the Youth programme (2000/2316(INI))

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52002IP0089&rid=3>

Date of document: 28/02/2002

European Parliament resolution on the Commission White Paper on a new impetus for European Youth (COM(2001) 681 - C5-0110/2002 - 2002/2050(COS))

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52002IP0223&rid=2>

Date of document: 14/05/2002

European Parliament resolution on Special Report No 2/2002 of the Court of Auditors on the Socrates and Youth for Europe Community action programmes (C5-0257/2002 - 2002/2125(COS))

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52002IP0608&rid=1>

Date of document: 17/12/2002

2003

Conclusions of the Council (Education, Youth and Culture) on 6 February 2003 — Contribution to the European Council on 21 March 2003 (2003/C 77/02)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52003XG0329%2802%29&rid=3>

Date of document: 29/03/2003

Council Conclusions of 6 May 2003 regarding the future of youth activities in the context of the new generation of programmes (2003/C 115/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52003XG0515%2801%29&rid=2>

Date of document: 06/05/2003

European Parliament legislative resolution on the proposal for a European Parliament and Council decision establishing a Community action programme to promote bodies active at European level in the field of youth (COM(2003) 272 — C5-0257/2003 — 2003/0113(COD))

<http://www.europarl.europa.eu/omk/omnsapir.so/calendar?APP=PDF&TYPE=PV2&FILE=p0031106EN.pdf&LANGUE=EN>

Date of document: 06/11/2003

2004

European Parliament resolution on the Communication from the Commission to the Council: Follow-up to the White Paper on a New Impetus for European Youth — Proposed common objectives for the participation and information of young people, in response to the Council Resolution of 27 June 2002 regarding the framework of European cooperation in the youth field (COM(2003) 184 — C5-0404/2003 — 2003/2127(INI))

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52004IP0119&rid=3>

Date of document: 26/02/2004

Decision No 790/2004/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 April 2004 establishing a Community action programme to promote bodies active at European level in the field of youth

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32004D0790&rid=12>

Date of document: 21/04/2004

2005

Conclusions by the Council of 21 February 2005 on Youth in the framework of the mid-term review of the Lisbon Strategy (2005/C 85/02)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52005XG0407%2802%29&rid=10>

Date of document: 21/02/2005

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States of 24 May 2005 meeting within the Council on implementing the common objectives for youth information

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42005X0610%2803%29&rid=8>

Date of document: 24/05/2005

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States of 24 May 2005 meeting within the Council on the evaluation of activities conducted in the framework of European cooperation in the youth field

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42005X0610%2801%29&rid=9>

Date of document: 10/06/2005

European Parliament legislative resolution on the proposal for a decision of the European Parliament and of the Council on creating the Youth in action programme for the period 2007-2013 (COM(2004)0471 - C6-0096/2004 - 2004/0152(COD))

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52005AP0396&rid=4>

Date of document: 25/10/2005

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on addressing the concerns of young people in Europe — implementing the European Pact for Youth and promoting active citizenship

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42005X1124%2803%29&rid=5>

Date of document: 24/11/2005

2006

Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on the implementation of the European Pact for Youth (2006/C 70/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42006X0322%2801%29&rid=15>

Date of document: 22/03/2006

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on the recognition of the value of non-formal and informal learning within the European youth field

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42006X0720%2801%29&rid=14>

Date of document: 20/07/2006

European Parliament legislative resolution on the Council common position for adopting a decision of the European Parliament and of the Council creating the 'Youth in Action' Programme for the period 2007-2013 (6236/3/2006 - C6-0273/2006 - 2004/0152(COD))

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52006AP0441&rid=18>

Date of document: 25/10/2006

Decision No 1719/2006/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 November 2006 establishing the Youth in Action programme for the period 2007 to 2013

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32006D1719&rid=9>

Date of document: 15/11/2006

Decision No 1719/2006/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 November 2006 establishing the Youth in Action programme for the period 2007 to 2013

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02006D1719-20061214&rid=7>

Date of document: 14/12/2006

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:02006D1719-20081225&rid=6>

Date of document: 25/12/2008

2007

Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, of 25 May 2007 on future perspectives for European cooperation in the field of youth policy (2007/C 314/07)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42007X1222%2802%29&rid=1>

Date of document: 25/05/2007

Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council of 16 November 2007 on a transversal approach to youth policy with a view to enabling young people to fulfil their potential and participate actively in society (2007/C 282/12)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42007X1124%2801%29&rid=2>

Date of document: 24/11/2007

2008

Youth in Action programme (2007-2013) ***I European Parliament legislative resolution of 2 September 2008 on the proposal for a decision of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Decision No 1719/2006/EC establishing the Youth in Action programme for the period 2007 to 2013 (COM(2008)0056 — C6-0057/2008 — 2008/0023(COD)) P6_TC1-COD(2008)0023 Position of the European Parliament adopted at first reading on 2 September 2008 with a view to the adoption of Decision No .../2008/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council

amending Decision No 1719/2006/EC establishing the Youth in Action programme for the period 2007 to 2013 (2009/C 295 E/25)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52008AP0369&rid=1>

Date of document: 02/09/2008

Decision No 1349/2008/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 amending Decision No 1719/2006/EC establishing the 'Youth in Action' programme for the period 2007 to 2013 (Text with EEA relevance)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008D1349&rid=4>

Date of document: 16/12/2008

Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council of 21 November 2008 on youth mobility (2008/C 320/03)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42008X1221%2801%29&rid=5>

Date of document: 16/12/2008

2009

Council Resolution of 27 November 2009 on a renewed framework for European cooperation in the youth field (2010-2018) (2009/C 311/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009G1219%2801%29&rid=12>

Date of document: 27/11/2009

2010

Promoting youth access to the labour market, strengthening trainee, internship and apprenticeship status European Parliament resolution of 6 July 2010 on promoting youth access to the labour market, strengthening trainee, internship and apprenticeship status (2009/2221(INI)) (2011/C 351 E/05)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52010IP0262&rid=1>

Date of document: 06/07/2010

An EU Strategy for Youth European Parliament resolution of 18 May 2010 on 'An EU Strategy for Youth – Investing and Empowering' (2009/2159(INI)) (2011/C 161 E/04)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52010IP0166&rid=2>

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on the active inclusion of young people: combating unemployment and poverty (2010/C 137/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2010:137:0001:0006:EN:PDF>

Council conclusions of 19 November 2010 on the European and International Policy Agendas on Children, Youth and Children's Rights (2010/C 326/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2010:326:0001:0001:EN:PDF>

Council Conclusions on access of young people to culture (2010/C 326/02)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2010:326:0002:0003:EN:PDF>

Council conclusions of 19 November 2010 on the 'Youth on the Move' initiative — an integrated approach in response to the challenges young people face (2010/C 326/05)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2010:326:0009:0011:EN:PDF>

Date of document: 19/11/2010

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on youth work (2010/C 327/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2010:327:0001:0005:EN:PDF>

Date of document: 04/12/2010

2011

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on the structured dialogue with young people on youth employment (2011/C 164/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2011:164:0001:0004:EN:PDF>

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on encouraging new and effective forms of participation of all young people in democratic life in Europe (2011/C 169/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2011:169:0001:0005:EN:PDF>

Resolution of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on encouraging new and effective forms of participation of all young people in democratic life in Europe (2011/C 169/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2011:169:0001:0005:EN:PDF>

Council conclusions on the eastern dimension of youth participation and mobility (2011/C 372/03)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2011:372:0010:0014:EN:PDF>

2012

Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the Governments of the Member States, meeting within the Council, on the overview of the structured dialogue with young people on youth participation in democratic life in Europe (2012/C 380/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:42012Y1211%2801%29&rid=6>

Date of document: 18/01/2012

Council conclusions of 11 May 2012 on fostering the creative and innovative potential of young people (2012/C 169/01)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2012:169:0001:0004:EN:PDF>

European Parliament resolution of 24 May 2012 on the Youth Opportunities Initiative (2012/2617(RSP)) (2013/C 264 E/11)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52012IP0224&rid=1>

Date of document: 24/05/2012

Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union PART THREE - UNION POLICIES AND INTERNAL ACTIONS TITLE XII - EDUCATION, VOCATIONAL TRAINING, YOUTH AND SPORT Article 165 (ex Article 149 TEC)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:12012E165&rid=3>

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Resolution of the Committee of the Regions on 'A Youth Guarantee' (2013/C 62/03)

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Council Recommendation of 22 April 2013 on establishing a Youth

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32013H0426%2801%29&rid=8>

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Council conclusions on the contribution of quality youth work to the development, well-being and social inclusion of young people (2013/C 168/03)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52013XG0614%2802%29&rid=6>

Date of document: 14/06/2013

Council conclusions on maximising the potential of youth policy in addressing the goals of the Europe 2020 Strategy (2013/C 224/02)

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52013XG0803%2801%29&rid=3>

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Regulation (EU) No 1288/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing 'Erasmus+: the Union programme for education, training, youth and sport and repealing Decisions No 1719/2006/EC, No 1720/2006/EC and No 1298/2008/EC Text with EEA relevance
<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32013R1288&rid=1>
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appendix 2 An application: at-risk-of-poverty and NEET in times of financial crisis for youth

A significant issue to touch upon is the effects of the 2008 economic crisis on the prospects of employment and poverty for youth in Europe. As Bukodi and Goldthorpe showed for the British male birth cohort of 1958, ‘whose first years in the labour market coincided with a period of severe recession, de-industrialization, and high unemployment, [who] would appear to have experienced various lasting disadvantages in their subsequent occupational histories’ (2011: 347). Thus, structural changes determine the subsequent employment history, especially for the first years of labour market integration. Furthermore, as Gallie and colleagues (2010) concluded, for the period of 1994 to 1996, ‘Unemployment increases the risks of poverty and poverty in turn makes it more difficult for people to return to work’ in 11 countries (2010: 1). There is a strong relationship between non-activity on the labour market and poverty. As it has been shown, the economic crisis of 2007 to 2008 seemed to have a polarising effect in Europe with devastating effects on youth cohorts in the most vulnerable countries (Therborn, 2014). Countries cope in diverse ways with times of crisis. Overall, the question remains what impact the crisis of 2007 to 2008 had on young people in terms of labour market integration and poverty within Europe. Here, we look at young people in the age group of 15-29 years and use the data of the IPOLIS youth module.

Our results show two important findings. First, there are large international differences in terms of NEET (not in employment and not in any education and training) and poverty experience for young people, and there is no clear line over the period from the mid-2000s (2004) until 2012-2013. Second, the crisis has had a polarising effect in Europe in terms of poverty and NEET with the highest impact in adolescence and late adolescence.

a2.1 International differences and link between NEET and at-risk-of-poverty

First, the relationship between young people not in employment, education or training (NEET) and those at-risk-of-poverty and social exclusion is measured. Young people in NEET are either unemployed or non-active. As Figure a2.1 shows, there is a strong association between young people in NEET and young people at-risk-of-poverty and social exclusion. In 2007, the Pearson correlation was 0.5718 and rose until 2012 to 0.7236 for 27 European countries (Figure a2.2). Overall, the picture becomes much more diverse, with more countries with high shares of young people in both at-risk-of-poverty and NEET. Rich well-organised/institutionalised societies (such as the Benelux countries and Nordic countries) have much smaller youth cohorts out of education and employment (NEET) and fewer youth at-risk-of-poverty and social exclusion than less-developed economies (such as Bulgaria and Romania) and more loosely integrated or less comprehensively institutionalised societies (like Italy, Spain, Greece, and Ireland) (Figures a2.1 and a2.2). Those countries experienced a boost in the share of young people at-risk-of-poverty and social exclusion from 2007 through 2012.

Figure a2.1 Relationship of NEET and at-risk-of poverty or social exclusion for young people (ages 15-29) by country in 2007

Figure a2.2 Relationship of NEET and at-risk-of poverty or social exclusion for young people (ages 15-29) by country in 2012

a2.2 Time trends in NEET and at-risk-of-poverty for selected European countries

A look at the time trend will give more insights on how the shares of poverty and NEET developed over the time span. We focus on a selected set of 19 countries, with nine representing Central and Nordic Europe and 10 representing Southern and Eastern Europe. All over Europe, young people experienced a sharp increase in unemployment over the first two years of the financial crisis (Scarpetta *et al.*, 2010). As Figures a2.3 and a2.4 show, shares of young people in NEET decreased for most of the countries from 2007 until 2008, though at different levels. For some countries, such as Ireland, Finland, Sweden, the UK, Lithuania, Hungary, Spain, and Italy, the share of young people in NEET increased from 2007 until 2008. In 2009, the share of NEET increased in all countries. However, from 2009 until 2010, all countries except Germany, Estonia, Latvia, Hungary, Finland, and Sweden, experienced a steady increase in young people in unemployment and non-activity. This trend was stable for most of the countries. Only Hungary showed an increase in the share of NEET and France, the Czech Republic, and Lithuania had less young people out of employment, education, and training.

Figure a2.3 Young people not in employment and not in any education and training by country, 2004-2013

Figure a2.4 Young people not in employment and not in any education and training by country, 2004-2013

Similar country patterns can be monitored for the share of young people at-risk-of-poverty and social exclusion. Countries such as Ireland, France, Spain, and Hungary had a constant increase in young people’s at-risk-of-poverty rate for the period from 2007 until 2012 (Figures a2.5 and a2.6). In countries such as Bulgaria, Denmark, Estonia, Latvia, and Sweden (for Sweden only until 2010 and for Latvia only until 2011), the share decreased from 2007 until 2012, but increased for the subsequent years. Countries such as Belgium, the Czech Republic, Greece, Italy, and the UK were hit by an increase from 2009 onwards. Thus, there are quite diverse patterns. However, some countries experienced stable growth in NEET and at-risk-of-poverty rates from 2009 onwards, such as Greece, Ireland, Spain, Bulgaria, and Denmark.

Figure a2.5 Young people at-risk-of-poverty and social exclusion by country, 2004-2012

Figure a2.6 Young people at-risk-of-poverty and social exclusion by country, 2004-2012

a2.3 Polarising effect in Europe in poverty and NEET for young people

Concerning the effect among young people in Europe, results in Table a2.1 show that NEET rates and poverty rates increased within the subsamples, especially for the Southern and Liberal countries from 2007 until 2012¹⁷ (such as Greece, Spain, Italy, Ireland, and the UK). For Germany and its smaller Central European neighbours, as well as for the Nordic countries (except Denmark), NEET and risk of poverty and social exclusion rates increased by less than two percentage points. In the case of Germany, the rates decreased by 2.3 (for NEET) and 1.3 (for RPS) percentage points over the time period. However, the impact of changes in risk of poverty is much more profound.

Table a2.1 Change in share of young people (ages 15-29) not in employment and not in any education and training (NEET) and at-risk-of-poverty or social exclusion (RPS) by country and age group, 2007-2012

	Percentage point change 2007 - 2012							
	15-29		15-19		20-24		25-29	
	NEET	RPS	NEET	RPS	NEET	RPS	NEET	RPS
Greece	11.6	14.3	3.4	9.9	14.7	13.3	16.3	18.0
Spain	9.4	13.1	0.2	11.2	12.3	14.4	14.0	12.6
Italy	5.0	6.5	1.2	2.9	8.2	6.7	5.6	9.2
Bulgaria	4.4	-12.6	0.9	-6.6	1.5	-14.4	7.1	-15.5
Hungary	3.5	6.9	0.5	5.7	5.5	4.3	4.0	9.8
Estonia	3.5	7.2	0.9	4.7	4.1	10.6	2.9	8.0
Latvia	3.3	3.2	0.2	9.0	4.2	4.0	2.9	-1.2
Portugal	3.2	4.4	-0.5	4.6	6.3	6.6	3.7	1.5
Poland	1.3	-8.6	0.5	-7.0	1.5	-8.4	0.5	-8.5
Czech Republic	1.3	1.1	1.0	0.1	2.1	0.6	0.4	2.9
Ireland	9.4	17.7	3.4	11.6	13.2	25.1	11.8	21.3
Denmark	2.9	6.7	1.0	5.2	3.6	4.9	4.4	11.1
United Kingdom	2.5	6.9	-0.3	5.4	3.8	11.6	2.8	3.5
France	2.2	1.9	0.9	0.0	2.4	2.5	3.0	3.1
Finland	2.0	0.7	0.9	-2.4	2.1	3.9	2.6	0.8
Belgium	1.4	1.8	0.9	0.8	0.9	0.6	1.8	4.0
Netherlands	1.3	1.9	0.0	3.4	1.3	-2.0	2.3	4.1
Sweden	0.5	-0.1	-0.2	-2.6	0.1	1.3	0.6	0.8
Germany	-2.3	-1.3	-0.8	-0.5	-3.3	-1.8	-3.7	-2.5

Source Eurostat, EU-LFS; EU-SILC, 2007-2012; [yth_empl_160] and [yth_incl_010]

Among the age group of 20-24 years and among the oldest age group of 25-29 years, changes in at-risk-of-poverty were more pronounced than among teenagers (ages 15-19 years). This age group is not fully integrated into the labour market and often live with their parents in one household.

In several countries, such as Greece, Denmark, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Belgium, France, and the Czech Republic, people in the late adolescent phase aged 24-29 years carried the highest burden in terms of at-risk-of-poverty rates (Figure a2.7). In the Liberal, Scandinavian, and some Southern countries especially young people aged 20 to 24 had the highest increases in

¹⁷ We use 2007 as starting point and track the changes until 2012 in order to see what substantial structural effects the crisis had on youth poverty and labour market integration. We do not differentiate between the different phases of the crisis (e.g. the different interventions).

at-risk-of-poverty and social exclusion rates. In Germany, Poland, and Bulgaria, at-risk-rates decreased at a lower level for younger groups than for the older groups.

Figure a2.7 Change of share of young people at-risk-of-poverty or social exclusion (RPS) by country and age group, 2007-2012

a2.4 Summary

Many countries, such as Bulgaria, Greece, Italy, and Latvia, entered the global economic crisis already facing high levels of NEET and poverty rates for young people. Yet the share of NEETs has sharply increased since 2008 for those countries and for many others. Given that NEETs are overrepresented in families with a low household income and high unemployment, this increase is clearly linked to at-risk-of-poverty rates. With higher unemployment and lower returns from capital, the crisis not only weighed heavily on incomes from work, but also made their distribution more unequal among young people. At-risk-of-poverty rates rose especially in the Southern and Eastern countries, where high levels of NEET and poverty rates among young people were already a problem.

However, the increase hit sub-groups differently. The highest burden in terms of experience of at-risk-of-poverty was carried in most of the countries by young people in their adolescence and late adolescence. While a recovery phase has commenced for some of the countries from 2011 onwards, for others increases in risk remain.

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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